

**ECUMENISM AS A PANACEA TO DISUNITY AMONG SELECTED PENTECOSTAL
CHURCHES IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA**

BY

AUSTIN EFOSA ERO

MATRIC NO: 223072

**A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY
SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES
IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF REQUIREMENT THE
DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY AT THE
REDEEMED CHRISTIAN BIBLE COLLEGE
MAIN CAMPUS MOWE, OGUN STATE
NIGERIA**

FIELD OF STUDY: SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY

JULY, 2023

CERTIFICATION

I certify that the research embodied in this project work was carried out by **AUSTIN EFOSA ERO** of the Department of Christian Leadership Studies, the Redeemed Christian Bible College, Redemption City of God, under my Supervision.

Pastor. Dr. Akintola Josiah Bolarinwa

NCE (English Religious Studies) (AOCOED).

B.Ed. (Guidance and Counselling / Religious) (UI)

M.A (Systematic Theology) (UI)

PhD (Systematic Theology) (UI)

Supervisor

Date

Pastor. Dr Akin Ogunsola

Co-Supervisor

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to God Almighty and my extraordinary family—my cherished wife, Mrs. Cynthia Igbaesiobo Austin-Ero; my sons, Master Jethro Uyiosa Austin-Ero and Master Joiada Oshiogimeyo Austin-Ero; and my beloved daughter, Miss Joy Eseosa Austin-Ero. Their steadfast support, unconditional love, and enduring patience have been an unwavering pillar of strength throughout this academic journey.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The successful completion of this research project was made possible through the generous support and contributions of many individuals whose involvement, both direct and indirect, proved invaluable throughout the academic journey. First and foremost, I extend profound thanks to Almighty God, whose abiding grace, favour, and strength provided continuous sustenance during the course of this study.

I am deeply indebted to my Principal Supervisor, Dr. Josiah Akintola Bolarinwa, whose commitment to scholarly excellence was evident in his meticulous review of my work, constructive critiques, and consistent academic mentorship. His guidance was fundamental to the development and completion of this thesis.

My sincere appreciation also goes to my Co-Supervisor, Dr. Akin Ogunsola, Registrar of the Redeemed Christian Bible College (RCBC), for his insightful supervision, unwavering support, and steady encouragement. I am equally thankful to the Provost of RCBC, Professor Babatunde Adedibu, for his invaluable input in sharpening the academic rigour of this research. My gratitude further extends to Dr. Olujobi Adeleke, Dean of Academic Studies, for his encouraging words, and Dr. Alaba Oti, Director of Academic Planning, for his thoughtful feedback. I also acknowledge the constructive contributions of Dr. Felix Akintunde and Dr. Dare Ajayi.

I wish to express special thanks to Pastor Solomon Ayinde for his constant spiritual support and encouragement, and to Pastor Daniel Oladapo for his remarkable assistance. I am particularly grateful to Jude O. Akanbi for his steadfast support throughout the project. My deep appreciation also goes to Pastor Olusola Duyilemi for his editorial assistance and to Dr. Patricia Ananga of the University of Education, Winneba, Ghana, for her careful and thorough proofreading.

I am thankful to the faculty and administrative staff of the Redeemed Christian Bible College (RCBC) for fostering a stimulating academic atmosphere conducive to theological research. The enriching scholarly environment at RCBC provided a strong foundation for my engagement with Pentecostal studies and ecclesiastical scholarship.

To my beloved wife, Mrs. Cynthia Igbaesiobo Austin-Ero, I am eternally grateful for your enduring support, patience, and loving care. Your encouragement served as a pillar of strength. I also extend heartfelt appreciation to our children—Jethro Uyiosa Austin-Ero, for his steadfast belief in my abilities; Joiada Oshiogimeyo Austin-Ero, for his inspiring words; and Joy Esosa Austin-Ero, for her sincere and uplifting prayers.

I am profoundly grateful to my mother, Mrs. Veronica Ero (née Enabulele), whose steadfast encouragement and unconditional love served as a continual source of motivation throughout this academic pursuit.

I wish to acknowledge with sincere appreciation the members of my parish, High Praise Sanctuary, Jesus the Alpha Area, Chapel of Love Zone, Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Rivers Province 4. My heartfelt thanks also go to Pastor Abraham Malgwi, my Area Pastor, whose spiritual leadership, friendship, and prayers have been a source of profound support. Finally, I express gratitude to the members and staff of Rigworld Training Centre in Takoradi and Accra, Ghana, for their kind understanding and words of encouragement during my academic engagements.

ABSTRACT

In recent times, the issue of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria has increasingly come to the fore with the clamor for ecumenism. Much of the existing research on Pentecostalism in Nigeria has focused on the origin of the movement and how they have affected other Churches especially established mainline Churches. This work focuses on ecumenism as a panacea to disunity among Pentecostal Churches, especially in Southwest Nigeria. The objective of this study is to present ecumenism as a panacea to disunity in Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria, also the need for the Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria to speak in one voice as regards issues affecting the Nigeria society. To highlight solutions to different approaches to doctrinal teaching and interpretation of the Bible, to find the remedy to unhealthy competition among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria and identify the prospects of ecumenism as a panacea for disunity.

This study adopted a descriptive survey approach, which is based on two approaches. The first part consisted of a series of well-structured questionnaires for respondents while the second focused on unstructured interviews through phone calls in getting respondents' responses. One thousand (1000) copies of the questionnaire were distributed, out of which 900 completed copies were retrieved for computing the results. Data collection methods focused on the open survey and questionnaire distributed based on equal representation of 250 copies to selected Pentecostal Churches; the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Deeper Life Bible Church, Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries and Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel) using 5 scales Likert scales.

The result revealed that doctrinal differences are considered as causes of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria with 77.9 per cent of the respondents agreeing that doctrinal difference in interpretation of the Bible is a cause of disunity, it also shows that 75.6 per cent agreed that unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria is important according to the Bible teaching. 79.9 per cent agreed that the quest for financial supremacy in Pentecostal space is another leading cause of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in South West Nigeria, 73.2 per cent agreed that competition in congregational size, members and size of worship centre is also a major cause of disunity among Pentecostal Churches and 68.7 per cent agreed that Pentecostal Church leaders are not willing to do away with doctrine to foster unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria.

The study concludes that Pentecostal Church leaders in Southwestern Nigeria should allow unity to reign among them for this is the will of Christ for His Church on earth. As ecumenism emphasises unity in the diversity of the Church, so we can say that what unit us is greater than what divides us.

Key Words: Disunity, Pentecostal Churches, Southwest Nigeria, Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN), Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN)

Word Count: 469

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title page	i
Certification	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgments	iv
Abstract	v
Table of Contents	vi
CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background to the Study	1
1.2 Statement of the Problem	3
1.3 Purpose of the Study	4
1.4 Research Questions	4
1.5 Scope of the Study	5
1.6 Significance of the Study	5
1.7 Limitation of the Study	6
1.8 Contextual Definition of Terms	7
CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURES	9
2.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study	9
2.2 Empirical Framework of the Study	10
2.3 Conceptual Perspectives on Ecumenism and Pentecostalism.....		18
2.4 The Emergence of Global Pentecostalism	21
2.5 Ecumenical Development in Nigeria	36
2.6 Expansion and Challenges of Nigeria Pentecostalism	40

2.7	Ecumenism and Pentecostalism in Nigerian Context	43
2.8	The Spread of Pentecostalism in Southwest Nigeria	55
CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY		61
3.1	Research Design	62
3.2	Population of the Study	62
3.3	Sample and Sampling Techniques	63
3.4	Instrumentation	63
3.5	Administration of Data Instrument	64
3.6	Data Analysis	65
CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS		
4.1	Results of the Research Findings	67
4.1.1	Questionnaires Analysis	67
CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSIONS, SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS		80
5.1	Further Discussions of Research Findings	80
5.2	Implication of the Research Findings	83
5.3	Contribution to knowledge	86
5.4	Summary, Recommendations, Suggestions for Further Research	95
5.4.1	Recommendations	95
5.4.2	Suggestions for Further Research	97
	Bibliography	98
	Appendix Questionnaire	104

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The term *Panacea* originates from Latin, tracing its roots back to the Greek word *panakes*, which means “all-healing.” It is derived from *pan-* meaning “all” and *akos-* meaning “remedy.” According to the Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, it refers to a universal solution or cure for difficult ailments.

The concept of *ecumenism* stems from the Greek term *Oikoumene*, meaning “the whole inhabited world.” It promotes cooperation and unity among Christians and has been in use since the time of the Apostles.¹ Historically, this term has been associated with movements such as the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople in the fifth century. The ecumenical movement strives to mend divisions within the Christian Church and foster mutual understanding among different Christian traditions. Ecumenism embodies unity within diversity, emphasizing that the Church of Christ should remain united, regardless of denominational distinctions. It aims to promote Christian unity by recognizing all Churches as part of one body of Christ.² It is also regarded as an initiative that fosters enhanced unity among various Christian denominations, aiming to achieve Christian unity. As noted by Mepaiyeda, it embodies the mindset of acknowledging other Churches as part of one body, grounded in our shared belief and confession in "one holy, catholic, and apostolic Church."³

¹ USCCB (United State Conference of Catholic Bishops), “*Ecumenical and International religious affairs*” 2023

² Austin .E. Ero ‘ *Definition of ecumenism* ’ 2022

³ S.M Mepaiyeda, “*Historical Analysis of Ecumenical Development in Nigeria*” JOLAN Volume 21 No 2 (2018) pp. 62-73

Disunity, on the other hand, refers to a state of discord that prevents effective collaboration.⁴ Among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria, disunity has become a significant challenge. Before completing His earthly ministry, Jesus Christ expressed His desire for unity among His disciples, as reflected in His prayer: *“And now I am no more in the world, but these are in the world, and I come to thee. Holy Father, keep through thine own name those whom thou hast given me, that they may be one, as we are”* (John 17:11, KJV). However, divisions began emerging even before the last of the Apostles passed away.

The issue of disunity can be traced back to the early Church, as evident in Paul’s letter to the Corinthians: *“For ye are yet carnal: for whereas there is among you envying, and strife, and divisions, are ye not carnal, and walk as men? For while one saith, I am of Paul; and another, I am of Apollos; are ye not carnal?”* (1 Corinthians 3:3-4). Paul identified three primary causes of disunity: jealousy, quarrelling, and factionalism. He emphasized that these behaviors stem from a lack of spiritual maturity and urged Christians to recognize their dependence on God. While individuals may plant and water, it is ultimately God who enables growth.

Over time, the Church has become increasingly fragmented, prompting theologians and leaders to explore ways to restore unity. This concern led to the emergence of the ecumenical movement, aimed at addressing divisions within the Church.⁵ Azino observes that there is a proliferation of Pentecostal Churches in urban areas of Nigeria, with doctrinal differences often resulting in further divisions.⁶ According to various scholars, doctrinal disparities have been identified as a significant factor contributing to the increasing fragmentation among members of different Pentecostal Churches. Observations suggest that the divisions within the Christian

⁴ Austin .E. Ero ‘ *Definition of disunity* ’ 2022

⁴ E. O Eregare, ‘Ecumenism and the Church in the Post-modern Era: Historical, *Biblio-Theological and Missiological Appraisal Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry* Vol. 15, 2017: 51–69

⁴ A. Efe, Proliferation of Churches and corruption in Nigeria: Understanding the irony, Academic, Education (Unpublished) Assessed 6th May 2015

community stem largely from differences in denominational affiliations, which have, in turn, had a profound negative impact on the Church. The Vatican II Council, as cited by Austin Flannery, affirms that Christ established only one Church, and any division among Christian communities undermines the credibility of the gospel message.⁷

The unity of the Church remains a fundamental biblical principle. Since the early schisms in Christendom, the landscape has changed significantly, with division and disunity persisting at all levels—from leadership to grassroots congregations. Many contemporary Christians inherit these divisions without fully understanding their origins, perpetuating denominational rivalry. The division and discord instigated by Church leaders, their representatives, and close followers appear to have taken deep root, extending even to the younger generation—many of whom have no knowledge of the original conflicts. Consequently, individuals often find themselves compelled to align with one faction or the other as the ongoing struggle for dominance persists.⁸ This research seeks to identify the underlying causes of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria and explore ecumenism as a potential remedy.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Much of the existing literature on Pentecostalism in Nigeria has examined its historical development, socio-economic impact, and the prosperity gospel. However, there has been limited focus on the issue of disunity among Pentecostal Churches.

This study aims to:

Propose ecumenism as a viable solution to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria.

⁷ A. O. P. Flannery, (ed.). *Vatican II Council: Decree on Ecumenism, Unitatis Redintegratio*. (Dublin: Dominican, Dominican Publications), 1988,452

⁸ N. I Ndiokwere, ‘*The African Church Today and Tomorrow, Prospects and Challenges*’, (Vol. 1. Nigeria: Effective Key 1994), 7.

Identify the reasons behind doctrinal disagreements and their implications for Christian unity.

Investigate variations in biblical interpretation and doctrinal teachings.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This research focuses on addressing disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria by:

Examining the reasons behind differing perspectives on socio-political issues such as poverty, governance, insecurity, sectarian violence, and gender inequality.

Analyzing variations in doctrinal interpretations, worship practices, and Church administration, including Holy Communion, finance, ethnicity, and linguistics.

Investigating the impact of unhealthy competition among Pentecostal Churches regarding congregation size, infrastructure, and educational institutions.

Evaluating the prospects of ecumenism and recommending it as a potential solution to disunity among Pentecostal Churches.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to address the following questions:

1. To what extent is unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria regarded as important in accordance with biblical teachings?
2. To what extent do doctrinal differences contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?
3. To what extent does the pursuit of financial supremacy contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

4. To what extent do competition in congregational size, membership growth, and the expansion of worship centres contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?
5. To what extent are Church leaders unwilling to relinquish doctrinal practices in order to promote unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

1.5 Scope of the Study

This research examines the historical development of Pentecostalism and the ecumenical movement in Nigeria, highlighting the prevailing challenges of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria. The study delves into the factors contributing to this fragmentation and explores its implications for the broader Christian community. Specifically, the research focuses on four prominent Pentecostal denominations—Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC), Mountain of Fire and Miracles Ministries (MFM), and Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel) (FGC). These Churches have been selected due to their significant influence and widespread presence across key states in the region, including Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Ondo, and Ekiti. Their doctrinal stances, leadership structures, and modes of worship play crucial roles in shaping the Pentecostal landscape. By analyzing their interactions, conflicts, and attempts at collaboration, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the causes and consequences of disunity within Pentecostalism in Southwestern Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The rapid expansion of Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria has been accompanied by a noticeable rise in doctrinal disagreements, leadership disputes, and internal divisions. These conflicts often stem from differing theological interpretations, with some scholars identifying key areas of contention such as the ordination of women, the acceptance of homosexuality, and the

perceived influence of Catholic traditions within Pentecostalism. As new denominations emerge, they frequently establish distinct doctrinal positions, sometimes in direct opposition to existing Pentecostal groups, further exacerbating disunity. Additionally, leadership struggles within these Churches have led to factionalism, with breakaway congregations forming due to power struggles among clergy and governing bodies.

This study contributes to ongoing theological and ecclesiastical discussions on ecumenism by exploring the root causes of Pentecostal fragmentation and offering potential pathways toward reconciliation. By examining doctrinal differences, leadership structures, and historical tensions, this research provides valuable insights into the broader implications of religious pluralism within Pentecostal Christianity. Moreover, it seeks to assess the role of interdenominational bodies such as the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) and the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) in fostering dialogue and cooperation among Pentecostal groups.

Through a detailed analysis of the challenges and opportunities associated with ecumenism, this research aims to offer practical recommendations for Church leaders, policymakers, and Christian organizations striving to promote unity within the Pentecostal movement. By identifying strategies for reducing doctrinal conflicts and enhancing collaboration, this study serves as a resource for addressing the growing divisions within Pentecostalism in Southwestern Nigeria. Ultimately, the findings of this research are expected to contribute to the broader discourse on religious harmony, helping to shape policies and frameworks that encourage a more cohesive and united Pentecostal community.

1.7 Limitations of the Study

The primary limitation of this research lies in its restricted scope, as it focuses exclusively on four selected Pentecostal Churches, despite the widespread presence of numerous other

Pentecostal denominations across Southwestern Nigeria. This narrow selection, while necessary for an in-depth analysis, may not fully capture the diverse doctrinal perspectives and organizational structures of other Pentecostal groups in the region. Additionally, financial constraints posed a significant challenge, limiting the researcher's ability to access certain essential materials, travel extensively for fieldwork, and conduct a more comprehensive investigation. The financial limitations also affected the ability to engage a larger sample size, which could have provided broader insights into the issue of disunity among Pentecostal Churches. Consequently, while the study offers valuable findings, its conclusions are drawn from a relatively confined dataset within a much larger religious landscape.

1.8 Contextual Definition of Terms

Pentecostalism: Pentecostalism is a branch of evangelical Christianity emphasizing the authority of Scripture, personal salvation, and the baptism of the Holy Spirit. It derives from the Greek term Pentecost, referencing the Holy Spirit's descent in Acts 2. A key belief is that Spirit baptism manifests through speaking in tongues and divine healing. This study identifies Pentecostal Churches as those emphasizing Holy Spirit baptism.

Ecumenism: Ecumenism refers to efforts promoting unity, cooperation, and understanding among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria. It seeks to bridge doctrinal differences and encourage inter-Church dialogue, worship, and evangelism. Despite historical divisions, ecumenical movements aim to foster collaboration. This study examines how ecumenism impacts Church relationships in the region.

Doctrine: Doctrine refers to the theological beliefs and teachings that define a Church's faith, practices, and governance. In Pentecostal Churches, doctrines shape salvation views, spiritual gifts, and worship styles. Differences in interpretation often cause unity or division among

Churches. This study explores how doctrinal differences contribute to disunity in Southwestern Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This research is anchored on Cardinal Walter Kasper's theory of spiritual ecumenism.⁹ Kasper posits that ecumenism is fundamentally rooted in Christian spirituality, extending beyond ecclesiastical diplomacy and intellectual discourse. He emphasizes that authentic ecumenical engagement necessitates recognizing the sanctifying and truthful elements imparted by the Holy Spirit, both within and outside the confines of the Catholic Church. Kasper highlights the significance of Jesus' prayer for unity, underscoring that unity is a divine gift and that Christians must, therefore, engage in collective prayer for it. Accordingly, he characterizes ecumenism as "the soul of the movement towards unity," asserting that Christians should take solace in the conviction that "what unites us is far greater than what divides us."¹⁰

From a Catholic perspective, Kasper draws upon the teachings of the Second Vatican Council, which conceptualizes the Church primarily as a communion. He affirms that the Church of Christ "subsists in the Catholic Church" while simultaneously acknowledging that elements of sanctification and truth exist beyond its visible boundaries. The Holy Spirit has endowed other Christian communities with distinct approaches to interpreting and meditating on Scripture, as well as unique forms of worship and devotion. These diverse spiritual expressions are valuable gifts of the Holy Spirit. Kasper advocates for an "exchange of gifts" among Christian communities, asserting that such mutual enrichment facilitates the Holy Spirit's guidance of the Church "into all truth" (John 16:13). Consequently, he concludes that Christians should be

⁹ W. Kasper, *A Handbook of Spiritual Ecumenism*, New York: (New City Press, 2007). 10-32

¹⁰ W. Kasper, *A Handbook of Spiritual Ecumenism*, New York: (New City Press, 2007). 20.

encouraged to engage in joint spiritual activities, leverage shared resources, and collaborate in all feasible aspects, in accordance with the degree of doctrinal agreement that currently exists.

This thesis conceptualizes spiritual ecumenism as the foundational level of ecumenical engagement, one that is predicated solely on the sanctification, baptism of the Holy Spirit, and faith. This form of ecumenism is prominently observed in prayer houses and miracle centers, predominantly within Pentecostal circles. Such settings typically do not adhere to doctrinal, dogmatic, or structural Church constraints; rather, they emphasize faith in an omnipotent, miracle-working God and His Son, Jesus Christ. Isichai appears to align with this interpretation, equating spiritual ecumenism with charismatic ecumenism,¹¹ which he distinguishes from structural or doctrinal ecumenism. This research posits that the prevalent disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria, particularly in the Southwest, could be addressed through the adoption of spiritual ecumenism as a unifying framework.

2.2 Empirical Framework

A vast body of literature has examined ecumenism through the lens of Church history. Writing from the standpoint of the Russian Orthodox tradition, an author in "The Orthodox Faith Website" defines ecumenism as a syncretistic movement aimed at fostering intercommunion among Christian denominations despite their theological divergences. The author controversially links the modern Ecumenical Movement, particularly the World Council of Churches (WCC), to Freemasonry, arguing that its underlying principles align with those of a secret society purportedly advocating for a New World Order characterized by a unified religion, common economic system, and singular global governance under the Anti-Christ.¹² This thesis contends that such an assertion is unfounded and misrepresents the true essence of ecumenism. Rather than being an occultic construct, ecumenism represents an earnest Christian

¹¹ F.I. Isichei, *Catholic Approach to the Charismatic Renewal*. Asaba: His Joy Books, 1988, 24.

¹² The Orthodox Faith "Ecumenism", <http://www.orthodoxfaith.com/ecumenism.html>. 15/07/08

effort to realize unity, in keeping with Christ's prayer "that they may all be one" (John 17:21). Moreover, ecumenism did not originate in Freemasonry but emerged among Christian missionaries who recognized that denominational divisions impeded their evangelistic efforts—a reality also observed within the Nigerian context. Deji Ayegboyin, for instance, documents that Protestant missionaries frequently accused Catholics of promulgating human traditions rather than divine revelation, revering Mary excessively, and engaging in what they deemed as fetishistic practices involving medals.¹³ It also emerged when Christians recognized the necessity of a unified response to challenges confronting the Church globally. Consequently, labeling contemporary ecumenical efforts in Christianity as syncretistic or influenced by Freemasonry misconstrues the interpretation of ecumenism, portraying it as contradictory to divine will. In light of this perspective, it is essential to contend that ecumenism has its roots in Christianity and represents a genuine initiative by Christians for their collective benefit.

Nikolai A. Berdyaev, in his work "Orthodoxy and Ecumenism," asserts that while Orthodox Christians and Protestants generally favor spiritual ecumenism, the Roman Catholic Church tends to advocate for a more structured, institutionalized form of ecumenism. He argues that institutional ecumenism is particularly challenging to realize among Roman Catholicism, Orthodoxy, and Protestantism due to the Catholic doctrine of Papal Supremacy. However, he suggests that institutional unity might be more feasible between Orthodoxy and Protestantism, as both traditions uphold a greater degree of spiritual autonomy.¹⁴ Berdyaev's work is particularly insightful, as it systematically delineates the forms of unity each Christian tradition

¹³ Ayegboyin. Deji Rediscovering and Fostering Unity in the Body of Christ: The Nigerian Experience, 19.

¹⁴ N. A. Berdyaev, "Orthodoxy and Ecumenism", in <http://www.chebucto.ns.ca/philosophy/sin-generis/berdaev/essays/orth328.htm>, 30/09/1927

aspires to, while also outlining the practical possibilities for their realization. His approach is commendably objective, making his analysis accessible to diverse Christian audiences.

Reports from the 1961 New Delhi and 1975 Nairobi General Assemblies of the WCC advocate for a model of ecumenism predicated on a conciliar fellowship of local Churches.¹⁵ In this model, each local Church retains its unique identity while participating in a shared fellowship characterized by mutual recognition of Baptism and the Eucharist. The WCC's vision of Church unity is particularly commendable because it fosters communion without necessitating doctrinal assimilation or hierarchical subjugation. This approach contrasts with institutional ecumenism, which would require either a wholesale return of all denominations to the Catholic Church or an indiscriminate acceptance of Catholic doctrines at the expense of their theological convictions.

Emma Ekpunobi, in "We Are Closer Than We Think: An Analysis of Contemporary Issues in Ecumenism,"¹⁶ classifies ecumenism into three categories: (1) the unification of Protestant denominations, (2) the broader integration of Protestantism with Roman Catholicism, and (3) the inclusion of non-Christian religions in the ecumenical dialogue.¹⁷ Ekpunobi also examines the Nigerian Church Union's role as a precursor to the country's ecumenical movement, detailing its interactions with the WCC. While his analysis is comprehensive, this research argues that the inclusion of non-Christian faiths in ecumenical discourse transcends the traditional definition of ecumenism and more accurately falls within the domain of interreligious dialogue. Ecumenism should be strictly confined to its fundamental purpose—promoting unity among various Christian denominations—rather than extending to the

¹⁵ D.M. Paton, (ed) *Breaking Barriers*, Nairobi, 1975, London 1976, cited in C.P. Ibebuike, *Understanding Ecumenism*, Enugu: Snaap Press Nig. Ltd. 2006, 7.

¹⁶ E. Ekpunobi, *We Are Closer Than We Think: An Analysis of Contemporary Issues In Ecumenism*, Enugu: Rabboni International 2001, 22

¹⁷ E. Ekpunobi, *We Are Closer Than We Think: An Analysis of Contemporary Issues In Ecumenism*, Enugu: Rabboni International 2001, 22.

unification of different religious sects, which belong to an entirely separate domain. In his work, *Anglican Spirituality: The Practice of Balanced Christianity*, Benjamin Diara asserts that the essence of ecumenism transcends divisions, emphasizing that God's mission surpasses the pride and exclusivity of individual Churches or denominational identities.¹⁸ The author presents a well-balanced argument, as these principles, along with numerous others, are central to the concept of ecumenism and should be a priority for all Christians in advancing the Church's missionary endeavors. This perspective is particularly significant, as the prevailing lack of unity within Christianity continues to pose a substantial hindrance to its missionary work.

Byang Kato, in his work *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, provides a comprehensive review of the development of ecumenical movements in Africa. Kato's study offers a thorough and meticulous examination of ecumenism on the African continent. He defines ecumenism as a "brotherhood" gathering that unites Roman Catholics and Protestants, and more specifically, as a movement aimed at achieving Christian unity by bringing all Christian denominations, including the Roman Catholic Church, into a single ecclesiastical body.¹⁹ He further argues that ecumenism is a product of the mission fields, with a series of ecumenical conferences held between 1910 and 1947. These conferences ultimately led to the formation of the World Council of Churches in 1948, which continues to promote ecumenical efforts globally.

Kato also points out that the ecumenical movement in Africa has developed within the framework of the All-African Conference of Churches. However, he critically observes that the absence of a universally accepted source of authority has led to a deviation from the true gospel of salvation.²⁰ This shift, he suggests, has redirected the focus of African ecumenism towards

¹⁸ B.C.D. Diara, *Anglican Spirituality: The Practice of Balanced Christianity*, Enugu: Computer –Edge Publishers, 2005, 132.

¹⁹ B.H. Kato, *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Kenya: Evangel Publishing House, 1975, 129-170.

²⁰ B.H. Kato, *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Kenya: Evangel Publishing House, 1975, 129-170

a gospel of liberation from imperialism and apartheid policies. Kato warns that this shift could give rise to syncretism and universalism, both of which he considers detrimental to the core message of Christianity. In addition to the author's various points, it is crucial to address the deviation of the All-African Conference of Churches from the gospel of salvation to a gospel of social liberation. If this issue is not confronted, the future of ecumenism in Africa risks compromising Christian doctrine, potentially leading to syncretism or universalism—positions that are incompatible with traditional Christian creeds.

In his article titled, *"The Missionary Origins of Modern Ecumenism: Milestones Leading up to 1920,"* Peter A. Heers asserts that the initial conception of ecumenical movements was introduced primarily by Protestant missionaries, who sought a strategy for advancing missionary work. Heers identifies key milestones leading up to 1920, such as the 19th-century Missionary Movements, Evangelical Ecclesiology (the Invisible Church), the YMCA, Student Christian Movements, the inspiration of the Ecumenical Generation, the 1910 Edinburgh Conference, the Cradle of Modern Ecumenism, and the 1920 Encyclical and Orthodox Participation.²¹ Heers' position is valid because the ecumenical idea arose among Protestant missionaries, who realized that their internal divisions were hindering their missionary objectives and sought a solution through the potential of ecumenical strategy. His reference to "milestones" emphasizes the various stages through which ecumenism progressed, culminating in its present form in 1920.

As a Greek Orthodox Catholic Christian, Heers is particularly concerned with encouraging his Church to fully engage in contributing Orthodox, Apostolic, and Biblical truths to the ecumenical movement, to avoid potential heretical deviations. Heers advocates for a periodic

²¹ P.A. Heers, "The Missionary Origins of Modern Ecumenism: Milestone Leading Up To 1920"
[http://www.orthodoxinto.com/ecumenism/HeersTheMissionary Root of Modern Ecumenisms. Pdf](http://www.orthodoxinto.com/ecumenism/HeersTheMissionary%20Root%20of%20Modern%20Ecumenisms.Pdf), 15/07/2008

review of ecumenical doctrines to safeguard against such deviations, stressing that this should be a collaborative effort involving not just the Greek Orthodox Church but all Christian denominations.

In his report titled “*Ecumenism*” to the Sobor of Bishops of the Russian Orthodox Church, Archbishop Vitaly critiques the origins and motives of ecumenism. Vitaly argues that ecumenism was not birthed from a genuine desire for unity or collaboration in mission but instead was designed to promote a pseudo-Christian agenda built on heresy, deception, and compromise.²² He further contends that organizations like the YMCA, YWCA, and the Boy Scouts were humanistic societies with Freemason influences, designed to infiltrate and corrupt Christendom with false doctrines and ultimately lead to a false unity. These groups, according to Vitaly, should not be involved in any ecumenical movements.²³

Vitaly’s assertions lack solid grounding. The current ecumenical movements, including those that formed the World Council of Churches (WCC), have not been designed to promote heretical doctrines but to address shared challenges faced by the Church in its global mission. It is important to note that the groups involved in the WCC sought unity not through deceit but through dialogue and cooperative efforts. Therefore, it is crucial for the Russian Orthodox Church and other denominations to engage with ecumenical movements with a mindset focused on understanding their roles and promoting Christian unity. No denomination can claim absolute doctrinal purity, although the Roman Catholic and Orthodox Churches may be closer to doctrinal consistency. It is vital for the Russian Orthodox Church to embrace the ecumenical efforts of other Christians and participate in fostering unity, rather than rejecting them. Despite perceived doctrinal differences, ecumenical movements should be encouraged

²² Archbishop Vitaly of Montreal and Canada, “*Ecumenism*”, A Report To The Sobor Bishops of The Russian Orthodox Church Outside of Russia”, <http://www.orthodox.info.com/ecumenism/vitaly.as-px>, 12/07/2008.

²³ Archbishop Vitaly of Montreal and Canada, “*Ecumenism*”, A Report To The Sobor Bishops of The Russian Orthodox Church Outside of Russia”, <http://www.orthodox.info.com/ecumenism/vitaly.as-px>, 12/07/2008.

to concentrate on theological foundations, as this approach holds the potential to resolve tensions rather than exacerbating them.

In his keynote address, *“Challenges Facing the Ecumenical Movement in the 21st Century,”* delivered at the Inter-Church Centre in New York, Samuel Kobia, General Secretary of the WCC, identifies key challenges facing the ecumenical movement in the modern era. He highlights the shifting center of Christian populations, the decline of older movements, and the emergence of new ones, stressing the importance of consistency in programming. Kobia emphasizes the need for unity in decision-making and the vital role of true spirituality in sustaining ecumenical efforts. His address provides a clear understanding of the current challenges the Church faces, which require joint efforts by all Christians to address the obstacles hindering the achievement of peace and unity in Christendom.²⁴ The real challenges Kobia identifies are valid and require a concerted effort from all involved in the ecumenical movement to realize the long-awaited goal of Christian unity.

In his article, *“The Future of Ecumenism in the 21st Century”*, Michaelson argues that contemporary ecumenism must adopt renewed forms of expression that resist perpetuating division and instead refocus the Church on its foundational mission. He asserts that achieving this goal requires a deliberate choice between adopting an ecumenically inclusive approach or prioritising institutional preservation.

Furthermore, Michaelson suggests that Church leaders must decide whether their actions will be primarily inspired by spiritual vision or propelled by organisational momentum. Ultimately, he emphasises that a decision must be made between pursuing gradual, incremental reforms or embracing transformative, deep-seated change if the Church is to realign itself with its

²⁴ S. Kobia, The General Secretary of The World Council of Churches, A keynote Address, *“The Challenges Facing The Ecumenical Movement In The 21st Century”*, Delivered at the Inter-Church Centre, New York, October 22, 2005,

ecumenical mandate.²⁵ This perspective is valid, as ecumenical movements must evolve to overcome the denominational barriers and biases that impede progress. If ecumenical groups can embrace these fresh expressions and focus on qualitative rather than quantitative change, they will likely see greater success in fostering unity. Adopting old, ineffective methods risks stagnation, whereas embracing new forms will ensure advancement.

Furthermore, in his article “*Ecumenism in the 21st Century: Theses for Discussion*,” R.V. Sinner presents twelve theses for strengthening ecumenical efforts. He argues that successful ecumenism must be based on trust, humility, honesty, and mutual accountability, as well as meaningful, concrete relationships with visible outcomes. Sinner emphasizes the importance of a common goal, strong theological foundations, and the active participation of laity and Churches in ecumenical engagements. These principles align with those outlined in the Vatican II documents on ecumenism, particularly *Unitatis Redintegratio*. Sinner’s suggestions are essential for the success of ecumenical movements, as they advocate for unity and progress based on trust, accountability, and shared theological principles. If applied effectively, these steps could significantly contribute to achieving the long-awaited Christian unity.

Finally, Early, in his entry on ecumenism in the *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Religion*, underscores the importance of brotherly love in overcoming divisions within the Church. This suggestion is critical, as only through collective effort, mutual understanding, and love can the fragmented body of Christ be restored.²⁶ The author aligns these assertions with the principles of ecumenism as articulated in the documents of the Second Vatican Council on ecumenism (*Unitatis Redintegratio*). It is important to affirm that these measures represent progressive and constructive actions; when fully implemented, they have the potential to foster the long-

²⁵ Grangerg. W. Michaelson, “*The future of Ecumenism In The 21st Century*” An Article Produced At Symposium Hosted By His Holiness Aram I, Moderator of The Central Working Committee of The World Council of Churches, New York; October 21, 2005

²⁶ R.V. Sinner, “*Ecumenism In The 21st Century: Thesis for Discussion*” A Work Presented To The Continuation Committee on Ecumenism In The 21st Century Held At Ecumenical Institute, Bossey, November 19, 2007.

anticipated unity within the Christian faith. Furthermore, Early, in his contribution to the *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Religion* on the subject of ecumenism, emphasizes the necessity of nurturing a spirit of fraternal love as a means of eliminating divisive elements that have infiltrated the Church over time.²⁷ It is worth reiterating the validity of the author's proposition regarding the indispensable role of brotherly love in healing the fractured and fragmented state of Christianity. This research upholds the perspective that such a recommendation is vital, as the challenge of disunity among Christians can only be effectively addressed through a collective commitment to mutual understanding and cooperation.

2.3 Conceptual Perspectives on Ecumenism and Pentecostalism

Numerous scholars have explored the concepts of ecumenism and Pentecostalism. Andre asserts that the term "ecumenism" was first introduced in 1937 by the French Dominican theologian Yves Congar and was later adopted and formalized by Vatican II in the Decree on Ecumenism, *Unitatis Reintegration*.²⁸ The foundational principle of ecumenism is the belief that Christ established a single Church rather than multiple Churches. Consequently, the Roman Catholic Church views ecumenism as a means to foster reconciliation among historically divided Christian groups through prayer, study, and dialogue, with the ultimate aim of reuniting them. Chitando and Biri define ecumenism as a theological framework designed to encourage communion and engagement among diverse Christian denominations to promote Christian unity.²⁹

Rausch emphasizes that the objective of ecumenical dialogue is not necessarily structural unity but the development of mutual respect and understanding regarding faith and practice. It seeks

²⁷ T. Early, "Ecumenism" in *Encyclopedia Dictionary of Religion* (Eds) Washington DC: Corpus Publications, Vol. A-E, 1979, p.1159

²⁸ B. Andre, Ecumenism in Jean Yves Lacoste, (ed.). "Encyclopedia of Christian Theology, Vol. 1." New York: Routledge. 2005, 472.

²⁹ E. Chitando, & K. Biri, Walter Magaya's Prophetic Healing and Deliverance (PhD.) Ministries and Pentecostalism in Zimbabwe: a preliminary study with particular reference to ecumenism. *Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 2016, 72-85.

to identify shared beliefs while acknowledging areas requiring further discourse.³⁰ Eregare, Ekpendu, and Adesina describe ecumenism as a pivotal movement within the modern Church, addressing the increasing fragmentation within Christendom, which contradicts Christ's original vision for His followers.³¹ Achunike characterizes ecumenism not only as a movement but also as an attitude of openness and receptivity towards Christians of diverse denominational backgrounds. It promotes meaningful dialogue and the sharing of spiritual experiences, allowing individuals to appreciate the richness of other traditions. Through this mutual engagement, ecumenism strengthens interdenominational relationships and encourages unity within the broader Christian community. Ultimately, it deepens one's personal commitment to the values and message of the Gospel.³²

Kaigama adopts a pragmatic approach to ecumenism, viewing it not merely as theological dialogue but as active collaboration among diverse Christian denominations. He interprets ecumenism as a practical means of fostering unity through joint efforts toward shared social, spiritual, and moral goals. This perspective emphasizes tangible cooperation in addressing community challenges, promoting peace, and advancing mutual interests. By focusing on common objectives, Kaigama underscores the potential of ecumenism to transcend doctrinal differences and build lasting Christian solidarity.³³ He highlights ecumenism as a platform for fostering collaboration among Christians from diverse denominational backgrounds. Additionally, he underscores its role in promoting cooperation and understanding between religious groups or denominations. Eregare affirms that ecumenical efforts must be purposefully directed toward the pursuit of truth, the promotion of justice, and the realization

³⁰ T. Rausch, *Global Catholicism: Profiles and Polarities*. New York: Orbis Books. 2010., 994.

³¹ E. O. Eregare, I. C. Ekpendu & S. Adesina, Ecumenism and the Church in the Postmodern Era: Historical, Biblio-Theological and Missiological Appraisal, *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry*, 2017, 51–69.

³² H. C. Achunike, *Dreams of Heaven: A Modern Response of Christianity in North Western Igboland 1970-1990*, Onitsha, Nigeria: *African-FEP*, 1995.

³³ Ignatius. A. Kaigama, *Dialogue of Life, an Urgent Necessity for Nigerian Muslims and Christians*, Jos: Fab Educational Books. 2006

of unity among Christian Churches. He emphasizes that these three pillars serve as foundational principles for meaningful and sustainable ecumenical dialogue. Without a commitment to these core values, genuine progress toward Christian unity remains elusive.³⁴

Operating within an ecumenical framework, Koffeman presents a distinctive view on the essential marks of the Church, stating that: "...unity, holiness, catholicity, and authenticity imply the respective qualitative indicators of conciliarity, integrity, inclusivity, and authenticity."³⁵ In light of this definition, it becomes imperative to affirm that ecumenism represents the Church's and the body of Christ's collective movement toward dialogue and the realization of unity among Christian communities on earth. The unity envisioned for the Church must extend beyond mere theological dialogue, mutual respect, and doctrinal consensus. It should also encompass concrete structural collaboration and interdenominational engagement. This form of unity promotes an atmosphere where differences in faith expressions and ecclesial practices are acknowledged and respected, fostering a deeper mutual understanding and commitment to shared Christian witness.

Denominations

Denominational identity, which once strongly indicated theological stance, worship style, organizational structure, and social affiliation, has evolved. While denominations are not disappearing, there is little effort to provide theological justifications for their existence. Vason suggests that contemporary denominationalism no longer relies solely on historical associations but is shifting towards new forms of organizational affiliation.³⁶

³⁴ E. O. Eregare, *An African Christian Church History: Seventh-day Adventist Cosmology in the Edo-Delta States: 1948-2012 & Ecumenical Initiatives*. Lagos, Nigeria: Christ Coming Books. 2013

³⁵ L. J. Koffeman, *The Vulnerability of the Church – Ecclesiological Observations*, *Scriptura*, 102(1), 2009, 404–415.

³⁶ W. Vason, *The origin of Pentecostalism*. Cambridge: Haward University Press.2010

According to Todd M. Johnson and Peter F. Crossing, the number of Christian denominations worldwide has seen exponential growth. In 1800, approximately 500 denominations existed, increasing to 1,600 by 1900, 18,800 by 1970, 34,200 by 2000, and 45,000 by January 2015.³⁷ Nnebedum states that these denominations span 238 countries, with an estimated annual increase of 270 to 300 new denominations. Within Protestantism alone, there are approximately 8,196 distinct groups.³⁸

The term "denomination" refers to a distinct Christian group characterized by specific doctrines, liturgical practices, and organizational structures. While denominations often use alternative terminology to describe themselves, the designation applies broadly to both established Protestant movements—such as Baptists and Methodists—and their numerous independent branches. Many denominations actively engage in evangelism. Jerome defines evangelism as the proclamation of the Gospel and the dissemination of religious teachings to convert individuals to the Christian faith.³⁹

2.4 The Emergence of Ecumenism and Global Pentecostalism

According to Babatunde Adedibu in *Introduction to Pentecostalism and Ecumenism*, Pentecostalism emerged in the early twentieth century with a strong commitment to being an "ecumenical revival movement within traditional Churches."⁴⁰ He emphasizes that the significance and acknowledgment of the Holy Spirit transcend denominational boundaries, stating that "the Church in all her divisions recognizes the Holy Spirit as essential to her life and genuine growth . . . Divergent theologies have no bearing on this reality, nor do variations in Church nomenclature. The universal need expressed by all Churches is for greater

³⁷ T. M. Johnson and F. Peter. Crossing, Status of Global Mission, in the context of AD 1800–2025. *International Bulletin of Missionary Research*, 2015, 29.

³⁸ O. E. Nnebedum, *Ecumenism in Nigeria: The Roman Catholic Contribution*. An Unpublished M.A. Project submitted to the Department of Religion, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, 2009.

³⁹ P. Jorome. *World evangelism* Oxford: Oxford University Press. 2002

⁴⁰ Walter J. Hollenweger, Cit in Babatunde Adedibu *Introduction to Pentecostalism and Ecumenism_2* p1 2019

spirituality."⁴¹ Adedibu further asserts that while the early Pentecostal movement embraced an "ecumenical spirit," this did not eliminate doctrinal differences, particularly regarding ecclesiology and sacramental practices.⁴² Additionally, he explains that Pentecostals interpret the outpouring of the Holy Spirit as a divine affirmation of the unity of the Church and its missionary mandate. This interpretation is firmly rooted in their biblical reference to the events of Pentecost, as recorded in the Acts of the Apostles (Acts 2:1-10).

These ecumenical principles were not confined to the North American context but were also embraced by early European Pentecostal leaders, including the Anglo-Norwegian Thomas B. Barratt and the Dutch Gerrit R. Polman. Adedibu highlights Polman's assertion that "The purpose of the Pentecostal revival is not to build up a Church, but to build up all Churches."⁴³ The ecumenical convictions demonstrated by the early pioneers of Pentecostalism in both North America and Europe cannot be separated from the broader ecumenical movements that emerged across Europe in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.⁴⁴ Furthermore, Vondey has noted the distinct hesitation among Pentecostals to apply the terms 'Church' or 'denomination' to their movement, emphasizing the uniqueness of their identity within the broader Christian tradition.⁴⁵

Pentecostalism, as described by Musoni, is a distinct Christian movement that originated in the early 20th century in the America.⁴⁶ The term "Pentecost" is derived from Greek and was historically significant in the Old Testament, where it referred to the Feast of Weeks—a festival

⁴¹ Walter J. Hollenweger, Cit in Babatunde Adedibu *Introduction to Pentecostalism and Ecumenism_2* p1 2019

⁴² Thomas Ball Barratt, Cit in Babatunde Adedibu *Introduction to Pentecostalism and Ecumenism_2* p1 2019

⁴³ Wolfgang Vondey. "Pentecostalism and Ecumenism" in Cecil M. Robeck, Jr and Amons Yong. Eds. *Cambridge Companion to Pentecostalism*,275

⁴⁴ Simo Frestadius. "European Pentecostalism: A European Past and a Pentecostal Future," *Pneuma* 42.3-4 (2020), 420-422.

⁴⁵ Wolfgang Vondey. "Pentecostalism and Ecumenism" in Cecil M. Robeck, Jr and Amons Yong. Eds. *Cambridge Companion to Pentecostalism*,275

⁴⁶ P. Musoni, African Pentecostalism and Sustainable Development: A Study on the Zimbabwe Assemblies of God Africa, Forward In Faith Church: In *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*. Volume 2, Issue October 2013.

observed on the fiftieth day, seven weeks after the Passover. However, in the New Testament, Pentecost takes on a different meaning, symbolizing the day when the Holy Spirit descended upon the early Church, as recorded in Acts 2. Pentecostalism is thus associated with "spirit-led" Churches that anchor their doctrine in Acts 2. A defining characteristic of these Churches is their belief in glossolalia, or speaking in tongues, which they view as evidence of the baptism in the Holy Spirit. This practice is regarded as an essential element of Pentecostal theology.

Furthermore, Alexander asserts that Pentecostalism, akin to other Born-Again Christian movements, upholds the doctrine of biblical infallibility.⁴⁷ It emphasizes the necessity of a conversion experience and places strong theological significance on spiritual gifts such as divine healing, prophecy, and exorcism.⁴⁸

According to Boyd's Bible Dictionary, the term "Pentecost" (Pentecosto in Greek) originates from the Greek word meaning "fiftieth."⁴⁹ In Jewish tradition, it refers to the festival celebrated on the fiftieth day following the Passover, commemorating the giving of the Ten Commandments at Mount Sinai. In Christian theology, Pentecost is observed seven weeks after Easter to mark the descent of the Holy Spirit, as recorded in Acts 1:1-4. The event of Pentecost signifies not only the coming of the Holy Spirit upon the apostles following Christ's resurrection and ascension but also its subsequent impact on the early Church.

Contemporary Pentecostalism is thus understood as a charismatic movement that highlights the visible manifestations of the Holy Spirit, particularly speaking in tongues and faith healing. Matthews Ojo traces the prominence of these characteristics to the early 1970s during a period

⁴⁷ D. Maxwell, The Rise and Fall of the Dutch Reformed Church (DRC): In the Victoria Circle 1888-1950: A Dissenting View of the Church's Alleged Invention of Chikaranga with Particular Reference to the Chibi Circuit, Unpublished paper presented at the New Dimensions in History Seminar Paper No. 5. Department of History, University of Zimbabwe 28 May 2004.

⁴⁸ P. Musoni, *African Pentecostalism and Sustainable Development: A Study on the Zimbabwe Assemblies of God Africa*, Forward In Faith Church, 2003, 49

⁴⁹ Boyd Bible Dictionary, 1980. 219

of charismatic revival.⁵⁰ Within this framework, the literal interpretation of scripture is paramount to Pentecostal beliefs.

Walter J. Hollenweger corroborates this perspective, arguing that Pentecostals deeply engage with the Bible, contrary to accusations that they prioritize spiritual illumination over scripture.⁵¹ He emphasizes that biblical texts are intricately woven into their prayers and theological writings.⁵² Matthews Ojo further describes Pentecostalism as a movement rich in charismatic expressions, often referred to as the Charismatic Movement, Neo-Pentecostalism, or the Born-Again Movement. However, he contends that these terms do not fully capture the nature of renewal groups within Nigerian Christianity.⁵³ De Petrella defines Pentecostalism as a distinctive branch of Protestant Christianity that has evolved into an indigenous movement characterized by intense spiritual enthusiasm, communal solidarity, and an anti-hierarchical ecclesiological structure.⁵⁴ Scholarly consensus indicates that Pentecostal revivalism has its origins in the 19th-century Holiness Movement, further shaped by religious transformations following the American Civil War.⁵⁵

Vason characterizes Pentecostalism as a Protestant renewal movement that emphasizes personal encounters with God through the baptism of the Holy Spirit.⁵⁶ This experience empowers believers for spiritual living and ministry, including manifestations such as speaking in tongues and divine healing. He asserts that Pentecostalism arose from the Holiness Movement of the early 20th century, fueled by revivalism and eschatological expectations. The movement's pioneers anticipated a spiritual renewal that would restore the Church's spiritual gifts and facilitate global evangelization.

⁵⁰ M. Ojo, *The End-Time Army*, Charismatic movement in modern Nigeria. Africa World Press Nigeria 2006,11

⁵¹ J. Walter Hollenweger, *The Pentecostals*, (SCM Press Ltd, London UK 1972)), 321

⁵² J. Walter Hollenweger, *The Pentecostals*, (SCM Press Ltd, London UK 1972)), 322

⁵³ M. Ojo, *The End-Time Army*, Charismatic movement in modern Nigeria. Africa World Press Nigeria 2006,11

⁵⁴ L. S. Vaccaro de Petrella

⁵⁵ C. B. Johns, *Pentecostal Formation*, (Wipf & Stock Publishers, Oregon, United States, 2010) 65

⁵⁶ W. Vason. *The origin of Pentecostalism*. Cambridge: Haward University Press. 2010

According to Lesslie Newbigin, Pentecostalism—alongside the emerging forms of Neo-Pentecostalism and Charismatic in Sub-Saharan Africa—is often identified as the "third force" within global Christianity, positioned after Protestantism and Roman Catholicism.⁵⁷ In this regard, Newbigin, in his influential work *The Household of God*,⁵⁸ describes Pentecostalism as embodying a third stream of Christian tradition. He situates it alongside Protestantism, which prioritises the preaching of the Word, and Roman Catholicism, which centres on the sacraments, thereby framing Pentecostalism as a distinct and complementary movement within the broader Christian theological landscape.⁵⁹ Drawing on Jonathan Mbiriyamveka's article published in *The Herald* on 27th July 2013,⁶⁰ Marongwe and Maposa highlight Mbiriyamveka's introduction of a striking term—'gosprenurship'.⁶¹ This term specifically references the growing perception of New Pentecostal Churches as highly profitable ventures. Within this framework, 'prophets' and their spouses—frequently styled as 'prophetesses'—are increasingly associated with displays of wealth and material success.

From the context of that article, 'gosprenurship' may be interpreted as the commercialisation of gospel ministry, where the missionary mandate is seemingly redefined as a profit-driven enterprise—essentially a modern-day, income-generating family business.

Nevertheless, my critique of Mbiriyamveka's perspective lies in the narrowness of his argument. While he rightly observes that some New Pentecostal Churches may operate under the guise of economic gain, his analysis fails to acknowledge the positive impact that many of these Churches have made. Numerous Pentecostal ministries identified within this category

⁵⁷ N. Leslie, *The household of God*, publisher: SCM press Greater London UK. 1953

⁵⁸ N. Leslie, *The household of God*, publisher: SCM press Greater London UK. 1953

⁵⁹ A. J. Kwabena. Chapter Fifteen: "Born of Water and Spirit": Pentecostal / Charismatic Christianity in Africa. The University of Pretoria. Library Services, 2013.

⁶⁰ J. Mbiriyamveka: *The Herald* journal April 2014

⁶¹ N. Marongwe. and N. M. Richard. PHDS, *Gosprenurship, Globalization and the Pentecostal 'New Wave' in Zimbabwe*: In *Afro-Asian Journal of Social Sciences*. Volume VI, No. 1. Quarter 1, 2015.

have significantly contributed to socio-economic development and the broader national advancement of their respective communities and countries.

Generally, Pentecostals hold a strong belief in the dynamic, ecstatic, and physical manifestations of the Holy Spirit. These are often expressed through fervent prayers, speaking in tongues, miraculous healings, prophetic utterances, visions, and frequent references to Biblical scripture.⁶² Such manifestations were initially unfamiliar to the mainline Churches. However, the spiritual experiences of divine healing and revelation associated with the outpouring of the Holy Spirit attracted many new adherents to the Pentecostal movement.

Another school of thought suggests that Pentecostalism encompasses a broad spectrum of denominations and theological viewpoints.⁶³ Within the movement, both Trinitarian and non-Trinitarian doctrines are represented.⁶⁴ Some groups practice only adult baptism, while others include both infant and adult baptism in their rituals. Although not all Pentecostals actively engage in glossolalia (speaking in tongues), the practice is widely accepted and never prohibited.

Pentecostalism also includes adherents from established Christian traditions, such as Catholic and Anglican Pentecostals, alongside a variety of independent Pentecostal denominations. There is no single global Pentecostal body that unifies all branches under one organisational structure. In Nigeria, the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) serves as an umbrella organisation for Pentecostal Churches; however, it is often characterised by internal conflicts, mistrust, and fragmentation. The PFN's decision to distance itself from the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) appears to have limited impact, particularly since governmental recognition—both at federal and state levels—continues to favour CAN. Nonetheless, in my

⁶² J. Mbiriya: 31

⁶³ Anderson Allan, *An Introduction to Pentecostalism: Global Charismatic Christianity*, Cambridge University Press, 2004;

⁶⁴ H. Cox, The Author(s). Published by Taylor & Francis. Florida USA 2004

view, several leaders within the Nigerian Pentecostal community have gained substantial recognition from government authorities. This is largely due to their significant contributions to national development, including social services, economic initiatives, and the establishment of educational institutions.

Walter Hollenweger, in his typology of the Pentecostal movement, categorized Pentecostalism into three principal streams:⁶⁵ classical Pentecostal denominations, the charismatic renewal within historic Churches, and newly emerging indigenous non-white Churches. His classification stands out for its inclusivity, particularly in acknowledging indigenous Churches as part of the broader African Pentecostal landscape.⁶⁶ The indigenous Pentecostal Churches of the Global South, especially within the Third World, represent the most dynamic and rapidly expanding segment of the Pentecostal movement. The Churches selected for this research—the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC), Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries (MFM), and Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel)—are representative examples of indigenous Pentecostal bodies. The phrase “non-missionary Churches,” once used to describe such groups, has been increasingly abandoned due to its colonial undertones. Instead, the term “indigenous Pentecostal” is now regarded as both appropriate and sufficient for academic discourse.

Examining the scholarship on the origins of Pentecostalism in Nigeria reveals divergent perspectives. One school of thought, as represented by Harold Turner, Ogbu Kalu, and Matthew Ojo, contends that Pentecostalism emerged as a local innovation through the spontaneous rise of independent prophetic or spiritual movements within communities where non-Pentecostal missions had already established Churches.⁶⁷ In contrast, another perspective holds that

⁶⁵ W. J. Hollenweger “*After Twenty Years Research on Pentecostalism*”, *International Review of Mission* 1986, 3-12

⁶⁶ W/ J. Hollenweger, *The Pentecostals*, (SCM Press Ltd, London UK 1972)

⁶⁷ H. W. Turner, *Religious innovation in Africa: Collected Essay on New Religious Movement*, (G.K Hall Press, Boston USA, 1979) 121-128, O. Kalu, *A Discursive Interpretation of African Pentecostalism*, *Mission Studies*

Pentecostalism was introduced by Western missionaries around 1932.⁶⁸ Nevertheless, synthesizing these two schools of thought provides a more comprehensive understanding of the movement's development in Nigeria. This convergence has given rise to the commonly employed terms "Pentecostalism" and "Neo-Pentecostalism," which reflect two distinct revival waves in Nigeria during the 20th century.

The first revival, dating back to the 1930s with the great Oke Ooye revival led by Prophet Ayo Babalola, and the second, occurring in the 1970s, these two revivals have shaped and led to the origin of Pentecostal institutional structures, doctrines, and practices.⁶⁹ The Pentecostal movement is characterized by its diversity, stemming from its independence, doctrinal variations, and fragmented organizational structures, which range from Episcopal to congregational models. This diversity complicates efforts to categorize the movement typologically. Since the 1970s, several terminologies have been used to describe new Christian movements. The movement's diversity has fostered varied Pentecostal perspectives on society and development. Despite misconceptions and misinterpretations, Pentecostals remain steadfast in their belief in the baptism of the Holy Spirit and its transformative power, which they apply both spiritually and socially. The second revival is widely acknowledged as the more influential, permeating multiple facets of Nigerian society. This phase is commonly referred to as the modern or Neo-Pentecostal movement.⁷⁰

However, it is important to acknowledge that distinguishing between the two distinct phases of the Pentecostal movement remains a complex task, primarily because there are continuous

2007, 20:1-39, M. A. Ojo, *The End-Time Army: Charismatic Movement in Modern Nigeria*, Trenton NJ: African world Press 2006

⁶⁸ J. D. Peel, *Religious and the Making of the Yoruba* (Indiana University Press, USA, 2003) 314.

⁶⁹ Mathew. A. Ojo, "The End Time Army: Charismatic Movements in Modern Nigeria" Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press; and "Eschatology and African Society: The Critical Point of Disjunction", *Ogbomoso Journal of Theology*, 2006

⁷⁰ Mathew. A. Ojo, "The End Time Army: Charismatic Movements in Modern Nigeria" Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press; and "Eschatology and African Society: The Critical Point of Disjunction", *Ogbomoso Journal of Theology*, 2006, p11.

shifts in worship styles and spiritual orientation over time. One of the most debated issues regarding the origin of the Nigerian Pentecostal movement is whether it stems from indigenous efforts or foreign missionary influence. Some scholars argue that the movement originated from a local initiative rooted in African spiritual consciousness, while others attribute its emergence to the impact of Western missionary activities. Still, another perspective suggests that Pentecostalism in Nigeria evolved through a synergy of both local dynamics and Western input.

Based on these varying viewpoints, it is valid to conclude that the most compelling explanation lies in the third perspective—that the movement was birthed from an African aspiration to reinterpret and revitalise Christianity through the Pentecostal experience of Acts Chapter 2, while drawing influence from Western Pentecostal literature. This hybrid emergence encapsulates an African desire to express religious devotion in ways that harmonise with cultural norms, without compromising the core biblical principles exemplified by Jesus Christ.

While Pentecostals often trace their spiritual lineage back to the Apostles, the modern Pentecostal movement finds its true historical roots in the late 19th century—a period marked by growing disillusionment with established religious traditions. Mainstream denominations, once known for their revivalist zeal, began to lose their fervour. Traditional forms of worship—such as impassioned singing, spontaneous testimonies, communal prayer, and extemporaneous preaching by laypeople—were gradually replaced by more structured and formalised liturgies led by ordained ministers trained in homiletics and influenced by critical biblical scholarship.

During this transitional phase, as large Protestant denominations increasingly catered to the upper-middle class, many working-class congregants felt alienated. These individuals longed for a more personal, emotionally satisfying form of worship that could address not only their spiritual needs but also their emotional, psychological, and physical well-being.

Pentecostalism—much like the earlier Holiness movement, which promoted the doctrine of sanctification as a second work of grace that eradicates the desire to sin—met these yearnings. Though Pentecostal Churches are inclusive of people from all socio-economic backgrounds, they particularly resonated with the disenfranchised, offering spiritual empowerment and a renewed sense of belonging.⁷¹

According to V.V. Thomas, the Evangelical revival that swept through the Western world⁷² during the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries is considered the ‘broader context’ from which the modern Pentecostal Movement emerged. In contrast, the Holiness revivals of the late nineteenth century represent the ‘immediate context’ or proximate background. Although spontaneous revivals were occurring in various parts of the world around the same time, Pentecostal scholars—predominantly from Western contexts—largely concur that the modern Pentecostal Movement originated in the United States at the dawn of the twentieth century. Scholarly interpretations of Pentecostal origins fall into two primary perspectives: the Classical view and the Societal view.⁷³

Gastón Espinosa offers a fresh and nuanced account of Pentecostal beginnings, reinterpreting the significance of the Azusa Street Mission in Los Angeles in shaping both the cultural and theological foundations of Pentecostalism.⁷⁴ Central to his analysis is the emphasis on the socially transformative dimensions of the movement. The late Swiss historian Walter J. Hollenweger identified African American slave religion as a crucial influence on the Azusa revival and the early Pentecostal tradition.⁷⁵ This perspective paved the way for Cecil M.

⁷¹ J. G. Melton: *Pentecostalism 10th March 2022*. (Editor of Encyclopedia Britannica)

⁷² J. Wesley (1703-1791) always had a mission to reform the nation and to spread scriptural holiness all over. This vision was carried out by his followers which resulted in revivals of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries

⁷³ V.V. Thomas, *Dalit Pentecostalism – Spirituality of the Empowered Poor* (Bangalore: Asian Trading Corporation, 2008), 35-41

⁷⁴ G. Espinosa, *The Origin of Global Pentecostalism*, Publisher Duke University Press, USA 2014

⁷⁵ W. J. Hollenweger identified Pentecostalism as having five roots: catholic, evangelical, critical, ecumenical, and black oral. “The Black Roots of Pentecostalism,” in *Pentecostals after a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition*, eds. Allan H. Anderson and Walter J. Hollenweger (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999), 36.

Robeck's evaluation of Azusa as an African American-led Church that championed a multicultural and inclusive community.⁷⁶

Espinosa advances this narrative by highlighting the theological contributions of William J. Seymour, whose vision during the Azusa revival established a radical social space. In this space, individuals from racially and ethnically marginalized backgrounds, women, the working class, and other disenfranchised groups could transcend entrenched, non-biblical boundaries of race, class, gender, and nationality. While these progressive ideals were not consistently maintained by subsequent Pentecostal movements—and even the Azusa Mission itself could not fully uphold them—they nevertheless laid a foundational framework for ecclesial reform and societal transformation.

A second and corresponding argument presented by Espinosa concerns the global expressions of Pentecostalism. Historically, most scholars before the twenty-first century regarded the Azusa revival as either the origin or the principal catalyst of global Pentecostalism. This perspective led to a dominant Americentric view of Pentecostal history. However, this interpretation has been increasingly contested. Allan Anderson, among others, argues that Azusa was not the sole origin of Pentecostalism but rather one of several global centers contributing to its emergence.⁷⁷ The proposition of a multi-community, global genesis of Pentecostalism has gained considerable traction in contemporary scholarship.

In his work, *Origin of Global Pentecostalism*, Espinosa offers an insightful analysis of William Seymour's role and the Azusa revival in shaping early Pentecostalism. He contends that Azusa had a profound impact on the worldwide expansion of the movement. Nevertheless, whether this argument effectively refutes Anderson's multi-community, global origins theory remains

⁷⁶ C. M. Robeck, Jr., *The Azusa Street Mission and Revival: The Birth of the Global Pentecostal Movement* (Nashville, tn: Nelson Reference and Electronic, 2006), 9.

⁷⁷ Anderson Allan., *An Introduction to Pentecostalism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 21.

debatable. More significantly, Espinosa invites an examination of the radical, countercultural, and socially transformative aspects of Azusa, emphasizing its function as a space that facilitated the emergence of Pentecostalism. Although many American Pentecostals did not fully embrace this dimension, vestiges of its transgressive nature persist within certain Pentecostal expressions.

Several scholars, including Vinson Synan, have traced the roots of Pentecostal Churches to the Holiness movement that predates 1901. Upon adopting Pentecostal beliefs, many of these groups retained core perfectionist doctrines.⁷⁸ Among them were predominantly African American congregations such as the Church of God in Christ, the Pentecostal Holiness Church established in 1898, the Church of God headquartered in Cleveland, Tennessee, as well as several smaller denominations. Originally founded as “second blessing” Holiness movements, these Churches later embraced the Pentecostal experience by incorporating Spirit baptism evidenced by glossolalia as a so-called “third blessing.”⁷⁹

Some of the early Pentecostal leaders emerged from Methodist backgrounds. Notable figures include Charles Fox Parham, who developed the doctrine of “initial evidence,” and William J. Seymour, the pastor of the Azusa Street Mission in Los Angeles, who played a pivotal role in globalizing the movement. Others such as J. H. King, who led the Pentecostal Holiness Church into the movement during 1907–1908, and Thomas Ball Barratt, recognized as the founder of European Pentecostalism, also preserved key Wesleyan teachings. Central to their theological stance was the belief that the experience of entire sanctification—or a “clean heart”—was a prerequisite for receiving the baptism in the Holy Spirit, with speaking in tongues serving as the confirming evidence.

⁷⁸ Synan Vinson, *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 2005

⁷⁹ Synan Vinson, *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 2005

In addition to these Methodist-aligned pioneers, early Pentecostal leaders from various denominational backgrounds also accepted the concept of second blessing holiness prior to embracing Pentecostalism. Though they did not emerge from Methodist traditions, they demonstrated equal commitment to Holiness theology and experience. Such leaders included C. H. Mason, originally a Baptist and later founder of the Church of God in Christ; A. J. Tomlinson, a former Quaker and founder of the Church of God (Cleveland, Tennessee); B. H. Irwin, a Baptist affiliated with the Fire-Baptised Holiness Church; and N. J. Holmes, a Presbyterian who established the Tabernacle Pentecostal Church.

Given the historical developments outlined above, it is accurate to assert that American Pentecostalism was essentially birthed from the womb of the Holiness tradition.

According to Vinson Synan, the emergence of the modern Pentecostal movement can be traced back to the year 1901 in Topeka, Kansas, and more prominently to the events that unfolded in 1906 on Azusa Street in Los Angeles, California.⁸⁰ While the initial conception of Pentecostalism is attributed to earlier spiritual awakenings, the defining moment is believed to have occurred either on the final day of 1899 or the early hours of January 1, 1900, when itinerant preacher Charles Fox Parham laid hands on a young woman named Agnes Ozman during a prayer session. It is widely accepted among Pentecostal scholars and adherents that Ozman received the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and spoke in tongues, which became the hallmark of Spirit baptism in Pentecostal theology. This event is often referred to within Pentecostalism as the “second Pentecost.”

The movement gained widespread attention six years later during revival meetings held in a rundown building on Azusa Street in Los Angeles. The individual credited with the active role of ushering Pentecostalism into public consciousness—often regarded as the "midwife" of the

⁸⁰ Synan Vinson, *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 2005

movement—was the Reverend William J. Seymour. Under his spiritual leadership, members of the congregation experienced the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and manifested speaking in tongues, further solidifying the Pentecostal understanding of Spirit baptism. Seymour, known for his unassuming nature, conducted revival services that extended over several years, often while seated behind the pulpit with his head lowered into an empty shoebox as fervent worship continued around him.

These meetings were characterized by spontaneous and emotionally charged expressions of faith—glossolalia (speaking in tongues), falling prostrate, ecstatic laughter, crying, and bodily convulsions. Vinson Synan vividly describes the Azusa Street revivals as unique and difficult to articulate in conventional terms. Vinson Synan, further gives this description of the meetings on Azusa Street, and the *peculiar behaviour of Rev. Seymour*:

A visitor to Azusa Street during the three years that the revival continued would have met scenes that beggared description. Men and women would shout, weep, dance, fall into trances, speak, and sing in tongues, and interpret the messages into English. In true Quaker fashion, anyone who felt "moved by the Spirit" would preach or sing. There was no robed choir, no hymnals, no order of services, but religious enthusiasm was abundant. In the middle of it all was "Elder" Seymour, who rarely preached and much of the time kept his head covered in an empty shoe box behind the pulpit at times he would be seen walking through the crowds with five- and ten-dollar bills sticking out of his hip pockets which people had crammed there unnoticed by him. At other times he would "preach" by hurling defiance at anyone who did not accept his views or by encouraging seekers at the wood-plank altars to "let the tongues come forth." To others, he would exclaim: "Be emphatic! Ask for salvation, sanctification, the baptism with the Holy Ghost, or divine healing". (The Holiness-Pentecostal Movement in the United States).⁸¹

The connection between the inception of Pentecostalism in Kansas in 1900 and its public manifestation in Los Angeles in 1906 suggests a direct link—Seymour is believed to have acquired his theological understanding of the Baptism of the Holy Spirit under Parham's

⁸¹ Synan Vinson *The Holiness-Pentecostal Movement in the United States Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1971, pp.108, 109.*

ministry in Texas. This continuity underscores the transmission of key Pentecostal doctrines from Parham to Seymour, and eventually to the broader movement.

Furthermore, numerous scholars attribute the wider acceptance of Pentecostal practices across denominational lines to the influence of Reverend Dennis Bennett, an Episcopal priest based in Van Nuys, California. His widely read book, *Nine O'clock in the Morning*, recounts his personal experience of Spirit baptism and played a pivotal role in introducing Pentecostal spirituality to mainstream Christian denominations. Equally instrumental in this diffusion was the Full Gospel Business Men's Fellowship International (FGBMFI), an organization that significantly expanded the movement's reach. FGBMFI's effective evangelistic strategy involved organizing breakfast meetings where prominent professionals and Church leaders were invited to hear testimonies and teachings on the Charismatic experience. Through these forums, Pentecostalism gradually gained social respectability and transcended doctrinal, ecclesiastical, and denominational boundaries. Eventually, various Christian traditions came to recognize and embrace Pentecostal spirituality as a legitimate expression of the presence of Jesus Christ through the Holy Spirit.

The relationship between the Pentecostal movement's inception in Topeka in 1900 and its expansion through the Azusa Street revival in 1906 underscores Seymour's connection to Parham's teachings on the baptism in the Holy Spirit. Scholars suggest that Dennis Bennett, an Episcopal clergyman in Van Nuys, California, was instrumental in introducing Pentecostalism into mainline Churches. His personal account of receiving the baptism in the Holy Spirit, documented in *Nine O'Clock in the Morning*,⁸² contributed to the widespread acceptance of Pentecostalism across denominational lines. The Full Gospel Businessmen's Fellowship International (FGBMFI) played a crucial role in disseminating Pentecostal teachings through

⁸² D. J. Engelsma, "*Pentecostalism: Its Identity, History, and Influence*", 2001

its influential breakfast meetings, which attracted professionals and Church leaders interested in charismatic renewal. This approach facilitated Pentecostalism's integration into various Church traditions and contributed to its growing legitimacy.

Understanding the historical trajectory of Pentecostalism from its emergence in the early twentieth century to its global expansion is essential in assessing its theological and doctrinal implications. Pentecostalism's origins are deeply rooted in the theological framework of John Wesley, particularly his doctrine of a "second blessing." Wesleyan theology posited that after conversion, believers could experience a subsequent work of grace leading to "sinless perfection." This second blessing was considered a distinct and transformative moment in the Christian life, requiring active pursuit and divine intervention.

Pentecostalism adopted and modified this Wesleyan concept, reframing it as the baptism in the Holy Spirit, with speaking in tongues as its defining evidence. However, unlike Wesley's Holiness theology, which emphasized sanctification, Pentecostalism reinterpreted the second blessing primarily in terms of spiritual empowerment. This doctrinal shift highlights the theological evolution that shaped Pentecostalism into a movement distinct from its Holiness predecessors while retaining key aspects of their teachings. The reinterpretation of the second blessing marked a fundamental divergence from Wesleyan perfectionism, establishing Pentecostalism as a movement centered on charismatic experience and spiritual gifts.⁸³

2.5 Ecumenical Development in Nigeria

Ecumenical development in Nigeria has its origins in the Great Awakening and the Evangelical Revival Movements in Europe, which catalysed the establishment of missionary societies and denominational Churches throughout Africa. The Christian message was introduced to Africans following the directives of the sending countries, resulting in the transplantation of a

⁸³ D. J. Engelsma: *Pentecostalism: Its Identity, History, and Influence (prca.org)1995p 55*

fragmented ecclesiastical model into Africa from the outset. According to Ayegboyin, Christianity in Nigeria can be likened to an extended but scattered family of diverse denominations, all professing allegiance to Christ.⁸⁴ In his categorisation of Nigerian Churches, Ayegboyin identifies no fewer than six major ecclesiastical traditions currently operating in the country: Roman Catholicism, mainline Protestant denominations, Ethiopian or African Churches, Indigenous African Churches, Pentecostal Churches, and neo-Pentecostal movements.⁸⁵

Given this diverse ecclesiastical landscape, any objective observer of Nigeria's religious environment would recognise Christianity as a divided household, characterised by divergent doctrines, belief systems, and internal divisions. Historically, the Roman Catholic Church upheld a long-standing axiom: *Extra ecclesiam nulla salus*, meaning "Outside the Church there is no salvation."⁸⁶ This was further reinforced by Origen's pronouncement: "Let no one deceive himself: outside this house [the Roman Catholic Church] no one will be saved."⁸⁷ This doctrinal position led to the Church's initial refusal to engage in ecumenical dialogues or cooperative actions, a stance that persisted in Nigeria until the latter part of the 21st century.

Conversely, Protestant groups maintained that the Roman Catholic Church had deviated from the true path of salvation. They embraced foundational Reformation doctrines—*sola fide* (faith alone), *sola scriptura* (scripture alone), *solus Christus* (Christ alone), *sola gratia* (grace alone), and the priesthood of all believers—to assert their theological legitimacy. On the mission field, Protestants often accused Catholics of propagating human traditions rather than divine

⁸⁴ Ayegboyin. Deji, *Rediscovering and Fostering Unity in the Body of Christ: The Nigerian Experience*, (Lagos: Wellspring Publication, 2000), p 17.

⁸⁵ Ayegboyin. Deji, *Rediscovering and Fostering Unity in the Body of Christ: The Nigerian Experience*, (Lagos: Wellspring Publication, 2000), p 18.

⁸⁶ O. John, "Christianity and other Religions: Contemporary Theological Currents in the Catholic Church and Reflections on the Nigerian situation", I.A.B Balogun (ed.) *Religious Understanding and Cooperation in Nigeria*, (Ilorin: NASR, 1978), 168-206.

⁸⁷ In Jesus Nave, 3:5

revelation, suppressing personal conscience, venerating Mary, and engaging in what they viewed as superstitious practices involving relics and medals.⁸⁸

This theological schism between Catholics and Protestants undermined the image and unity of Christianity in Nigeria during its formative stages, creating an opening for the significant spread of Islam. The lack of a unified Christian voice led to limited recognition by political authorities in contrast to the favour shown to Islam. This disparity partly explains the Colonial administration's embargo on Christian evangelisation in Northern Nigeria, which it justified by citing the region's existing political and religious structures.

Nonetheless, there were early indications of ecumenical engagement among missionary bodies. A notable example was the relationship between Anglican and Roman Catholic missionaries. Bishop Samuel Ajayi Crowther, in a remarkable gesture of goodwill, offered temporary accommodation in 1884 to Catholic missionaries newly arrived in Lokoja at the Holy Trinity Anglican Church.⁸⁹ Crowther's ecumenical vision was grounded in the belief that cooperative efforts among denominations would accelerate the spread of the gospel, acknowledging that no single denomination could evangelise the entire nation independently. This act of hospitality significantly advanced Anglican-Catholic relations and contributed to subsequent Christian unity efforts, including the establishment of the Bible Society.

One of the most prominent examples of inter-denominational collaboration occurred in 1885, when Bishop Crowther, an Anglican, voluntarily granted a parcel of land—originally gifted to him by the Obi of Onitsha—to the Roman Catholic mission under Father Joseph Lutz. This act became emblematic of practical ecumenism in Nigeria.⁹⁰

⁸⁸ Ayegboyin. *Deji Rediscovering and Fostering Unity in the Body of Christ: The Nigerian Experience*, (Lagos: Wellspring Publication, 2000), p 19.

⁸⁹ D. Akamisoko, C. S Ajayi in the Lokoja Area, (Ibadan: Sefer Books Ltd, 2002), 84.

⁹⁰ G.E. Igwe., *Church Union in Nigeria*, (Enugu: Ark Publication, 2000), 4.

The turn of the 20th century marked a significant era in the development of ecumenical initiatives in Nigeria. This period was shaped by the influence of Protestant missionaries who, inspired by the international and multi-denominational Edinburgh Missionary Conference of 1910, convened a similar gathering in Nigeria. Organised by the Scottish Presbyterian Mission in Calabar, the conference aimed to discuss matters pertaining to mission work. Delegates at the meeting expressed strong support for increased fellowship and cooperation among missionary bodies. Participating denominations included the Anglicans, Qua Iboe, Primitive Methodists, and the United Free Church of Scotland. During the 1911 preliminary session, Mr. A. W. Wilkie encapsulated the ecumenical spirit by stating:

*“We are not here primarily to establish in Africa, Presbyterianism, or Methodism or any other ‘ism’, but to preach Christ and take a lowly place, under the guidance of the Holy Spirit of God, in laying the foundation of a Church, which shall not be foreign to the African.”*⁹¹

Perhaps the most impactful aspect of Nigeria’s ecumenical journey was the establishment of united ministerial training institutions. The first of such efforts emerged in 1948 at Awka, where Methodist, Presbyterian, and Anglican traditions from Eastern Nigeria initiated joint theological training. By 1950, this effort culminated in the establishment of Trinity College in Umuahia. In Western Nigeria, a merger of similar denominational institutions led to the founding of Immanuel College of Theology in 1958. Initially operating from temporary quarters in Kudeti, Ibadan, the college relocated in 1964 to its permanent site adjacent to the University of Ibadan. These joint seminaries have since become instrumental in nurturing ecumenical thought, promoting shared learning, and fostering theological unity among future leaders of the United Church.

⁹¹ A.S. Oyalana, “Attempts at Church Ecumenism in Nigeria 1909-1965,” in Orita, XVIII, 1988, 38-39.

2.6 Expansion and Challenges of Nigerian Pentecostalism

According to Isichei, the historical development of Christianity in Africa cannot be examined without acknowledging its global dimensions, particularly the foundational interactions with Europeans. During the mid-fifteenth century, captives taken by the Portuguese to São Tomé and Cape Verde were converted to Christianity and later trained as clergy in Portugal. These islands evolved into independent dioceses by the mid-sixteenth century and subsequently supplied priests for the African mainland. The Portuguese also introduced Christianity to the royal court of the Bini Kingdom in 1515, resulting in a modest number of conversions during the sixteenth century.⁹² Similarly, Christianity gained limited ground as a court religion within the neighbouring Itsekiri kingdom of Warri.

Isichei further asserts that as European expansion progressed across the continent, isolated Christian communities emerged, consisting of European settlers, Afro-Europeans, and indigenous converts.⁹³ In the French territories of Gorée and St. Louis, located in present-day Senegal, a number of practicing Catholics were recorded.⁹⁴ On the Gold Coast, where European forts were established primarily for commercial activities, mixed-race Africans also embraced Christianity. Beginning in the eighteenth century, individual European and American missionaries introduced various Protestant denominations to West Africa. One of the earliest of these was Thomas Thompson, an Anglican missionary who arrived on the Gold Coast in 1752. Later, Thomas Birch Freeman, a biracial British missionary born in 1809, introduced Methodism to the Gold Coast in 1838 and to Yorubaland in 1842. In 1843, Henry Townsend, another Anglican missionary, arrived at Badagry. Additionally, the Basel Mission, founded in

⁹² E. Isichei. *A history of Christianity in Africa: From antiquity to the present*. Grand Rapids, Mich: Eerdmans, 1995.

⁹³ E. Isichei. *A history of Christianity in Africa: From antiquity to the present*. Grand Rapids, Mich: Eerdmans, 1995.

⁹⁴ E. Isichei. *A history of Christianity in Africa: From antiquity to the present*. Grand Rapids, Mich: Eerdmans, 1995.

1815, dispatched four missionaries to the Gold Coast in 1828, setting the groundwork for what would eventually become the Presbyterian Church of Ghana.

Although the term "African Pentecostalism" is commonly used to describe a wide spectrum of pneumatic Christian expressions across the continent, it encompasses various movements with distinct historical trajectories. Broadly, three principal categories of Churches fall under the Pentecostal umbrella in Africa. The first comprises Spirit-empowered movements that either developed independently or emerged from existing Western mission Churches. These are generally referred to as African Initiated or Independent Churches (AICs). The second group includes Churches established by classical Pentecostal denominations of Western origin, such as the Assemblies of God, Four Square Gospel Church, and the Apostolic Church. The final group consists of neo-Pentecostal or charismatic Churches, which represent a newer wave of Pentecostal expression across the continent.

Omenyo observes that AICs have sustained African traditional beliefs, particularly the concept of an 'enchanted universe' where supernatural forces influence human destiny. These Churches interpret Christianity through the lens of African Traditional Religion (ATR), asserting that indigenous spirituality is central to African identity.⁹⁵ By contrast, missionary Churches often framed conversion as an adoption of Western values, portraying ATR as idolatry.⁹⁶ Williamson (1965) describes this dynamic:

"The invitation to accept the Christian religion was also a call to participate in a Western interpretation of reality. Converts were not merely required to abandon the worship of many gods for the worship of One God but were taught to regard traditional religion as engagement with nonentities."⁹⁷

⁹⁵ C. Omenyo, 'African Pentecostalism', in C.M. Robeck & A. Young, The Cambridge Companion to Pentecostalism, Cambridge University Press, New York. 2014, 132–151,

⁹⁶ Bediako, *Christianity in Africa: The renewal of a non-Western religion*, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh. 1995

⁹⁷ S. G. Williamson, *Akan religion and the Christian faith: A comparative study of the impact of two religions*, Ghana University Press, Accra. 1965

Hollenweger contends that the Pentecostal movement's extraordinary growth in the Global South stems from its African roots and respect for indigenous heritage. The 1906 Azusa Street Revival, led by African American preacher William J. Seymour, played a pivotal role in shaping global Pentecostalism. Seymour's spirituality, influenced by black religious culture in the southern United States, integrated indigenous African elements such as trance, ecstasy, visions, and healing, aligning with biblical traditions. Alvarado (2016) describes this fusion as an adaptive transformation of African spirituality in a new context.⁹⁸

Cox further argues that religion provides a crucial framework for human behaviour, with African Pentecostalism exemplifying the persistence of primal religious concepts even in technologically advanced societies. He posits that African Pentecostalism cannot be fully understood without acknowledging its deep connections to Africa's spiritual heritage.⁹⁹

Seymour, born to parents who had once been enslaved, was deeply shaped by the religious life of Southern Black communities (Alvarado 2016:338).¹⁰⁰ Within this cultural context, a unique integration of African traditional spiritual elements had already become embedded within Protestant Christian worship. Practices such as trance states, ecstatic experiences, visionary encounters, dream interpretations, and healing rituals had continued in alignment with similar expressions found in the Bible. African Americans did not simply preserve these spiritual expressions as historical remnants; rather, they actively reinterpreted and reshaped them to resonate with their present realities, merging African spiritual consciousness with the socio-religious structures of their new context.¹⁰¹

⁹⁸ J. K. Asamoah-Gyadu, 'Pentecostalism and the influence of primal realities in Africa', in H.D. Hunter & N. Ormerod (eds.), *The many faces of global Pentecostalism*, pp. 139–161, CPT, Cleveland. 2013

⁹⁹ H. Cox, *Fire from heaven: The rise of Pentecostal spirituality and the reshaping of Christianity in the twenty-first century*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, 1995, 100

¹⁰⁰ J. E. Alvarado, 'Exploring Africanisms in Latin American Pentecostalism,' in V. Synan & M. Álvarez (eds.), *Global Renewal Christianity: Spirit-empowered movements past, present, and future*, vol. 2: Latin America, Charisma House, Lake Mary. 2016, 337–353

¹⁰¹ A. H. Anderson. *An introduction to Pentecostalism*, 2nd ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. 2013

Cox argues that religion offers a critical lens through which to understand human behaviour, as individuals navigate their lives through frameworks of meaning and value—without which human experience would lack coherence.¹⁰² African Pentecostalism, when understood through this lens, reveals its coherence through the enduring vitality of primal religious thought, even within a society influenced by scientific rationalism and technological advancement. Cox further contends that Africa’s primal spirituality forms the foundational ethos of Pentecostal expression on the continent. This spiritual foundation imparts a unique character to African Pentecostalism, making it essential to acknowledge the enduring influence of indigenous African spiritualities in any attempt to interpret Pentecostal belief and practice.¹⁰³

2.7 Ecumenism and Pentecostalism in the Nigerian Context

The Origins of Pentecostalism in Nigeria

The 1910s–1920s: In the early 1910s, an Anglican deacon initiated a locally-rooted prophetic movement that eventually evolved into the Christ Army Church. The influenza pandemic of 1918 ignited a series of revivalist activities across both mission Churches and the Christ Army Church. During this period, spiritually-driven movements flourished, notably the groups referred to in Yoruba as *Aladura*—meaning “people who pray.” Among the earliest *Aladura* Churches were the Eternal Sacred Order of the Cherubim and Seraphim, established in 1925, and the Church of the Lord (*Aladura*), founded in 1930. Around 1918, an Anglican layman organized a prayer circle named the Precious Stone (or Diamond) Society, with the primary aim of ministering to victims of the influenza outbreak. By the early 1920s, this group had severed ties with the Anglican Church and aligned itself with Faith Tabernacle, a holiness movement headquartered in Philadelphia, USA.

¹⁰² H. Cox, *Fire from heaven: The rise of Pentecostal spirituality and the reshaping of Christianity in the twenty-first century*, Addison-Wesley, Reading. 1995

¹⁰³

The 1930s–1940s: During the 1930s, Joseph Babalola—affiliated with Faith Tabernacle— spearheaded a large-scale revival movement that led to the conversion of thousands across Nigeria.¹⁰⁴ In 1932, his revivalist campaign fostered a temporary affiliation with the Apostolic Church of Great Britain, formed in response to mounting tensions with colonial authorities. However, the partnership eventually collapsed due to disagreements over the use of Western medicine.¹⁰⁵ In 1941, Babalola established the autonomous Christ Apostolic Church, which, by 1990, reportedly had a membership exceeding one million adherents (Anderson 2001: 86–87).¹⁰⁶ This period also witnessed the emergence of foreign Pentecostal missions, including the Welsh Apostolic Church in 1931, the Assemblies of God in 1939.

The 1950s: The 1950s marked the introduction of the Celestial Church of Christ (CCC) to Southwestern Nigeria from Benin.¹⁰⁷ The Church experienced rapid growth, expanding into Northern Nigeria and emerging as one of the most prominent *Aladura* Churches on the continent. In 1952, Pa Josiah Akindayomi—a former adherent of the Cherubim and Seraphim Society—established the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). Under the subsequent leadership of Enoch Adejare Adeboye, the RCCG embraced an increasingly Pentecostal doctrine and worship style, expanding from approximately 42 congregations in 1980 to over 7,000 by 2004. By this time, the Church had also extended its presence to over 90 nations, including the United States.¹⁰⁸

The 1960s–1970s: The emergence of Pentecostalism in Nigeria during the 1960s and 1970s can be traced to evangelical student revivals that catalyzed the formation of new independent

¹⁰⁴ A. H. Anderson, *African Reformation: African Initiated Christianity in the 20th Century* (Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 2001)

¹⁰⁵ A. H. Anderson, *African Reformation: African Initiated Christianity in the 20th Century* (Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 2001)

¹⁰⁶ A. H. Anderson, *African Reformation: African Initiated Christianity in the 20th Century* (Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 2001)

¹⁰⁷ Anderson 2001: 85; Murphy, March 25, 2006; Mahtani, April 26, 2005; Ojo 2004: 4

¹⁰⁸ Anderson 2001: 85; Murphy, March 25, 2006; Mahtani, April 26, 2005; Ojo 2004: 4

Churches. A pivotal figure in this expansion was Benson Idahosa, recognized as one of Africa's most influential Pentecostal leaders. In 1972, he founded the Church of God Mission International. Two years later, in 1974, the Grace of God Ministry was established in Eastern Nigeria as part of the growing Pentecostal landscape. The Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC), formed in 1975, rapidly expanded and by 1993, had grown to become one of Nigeria's largest neo-Pentecostal congregations, boasting an estimated membership of 350,000.

The 1980s–Present: The 1980s and 1990s witnessed the continued rise of charismatic Churches across Nigeria. One significant milestone was the establishment of Living Faith Outreach Worldwide, commonly referred to as “Winners’ Chapel,” by David Oyedepo in 1982. By 1999, the Church had constructed the Faith Tabernacle in Lagos, a massive 50,000-seat auditorium, symbolizing the architectural and demographic growth of Pentecostalism in the country.¹⁰⁹

Findings from the Pew Forum's 2006 Pentecostal survey revealed that Renewalists—which include both Pentecostals and Charismatics—comprised approximately 30% of Nigeria's population.¹¹⁰ Among Protestant denominations, roughly 60% of adherents were either Pentecostal or Charismatic, and about 30% of surveyed Catholics in Nigeria were identified as Charismatic.¹¹¹

Pentecostalism has evolved into a major religious force in Nigeria in the 21st century, underpinned by its exponential growth and widespread presence across urban centers. Its adherents frequently exhibit a profound sense of contentment and spiritual fervor. With its membership now numbering in the millions, Pentecostalism has emerged as a dominant religious movement in contemporary Nigeria.¹¹² A 2011 Pew Forum study on global

¹⁰⁹ Phillips, Nov. 30, 1999; Ojo 2004: 4

¹¹⁰ P. Forum on Religion and Public Life, *Global Christianity: A report on the size and distribution of the World Christian Population*, 2011, p 67

¹¹¹ P. Forum on Religion and Public Life, *Global Christianity: A report on the size and distribution of the World Christian Population*, 2011, p 67

¹¹² J. I. Elaigwu, *Essay in Governance and Society*, (Nigeria: Adonis & Abbey Publishers, 20212) 45

Christianity estimated the number of classical Pentecostals globally at 279 million—representing approximately 4% of the global population and 12.8% of the worldwide Christian demographic.¹¹³

Further data from Barrett and Johnson estimated that Pentecostals comprise at least 25% of the global Christian population.¹¹⁴ Historian Vinson Synan, speaking at the 1998 Pentecostal World Conference in Seoul,¹¹⁵ supported this assertion, while David Barrett projected that by 2025, the number of Pentecostal adherents could reach 1.14 billion, or 44% of the global Christian population. According to the 2011 Pew Forum analysis conducted at Gordon-Conwell Theological Seminary, the global population of Pentecostals stood at approximately 279 million, with Charismatics totaling over 305 million.¹¹⁶

Harvey Cox further argued that by the next century, the number of Pentecostal believers—across its diverse expressions—may exceed that of both Catholic and mainline Protestant denominations.¹¹⁷ In the Nigerian context, the deepening socio-economic crises and the government’s failure to mitigate these conditions have fueled the Pentecostal surge. For many Africans, spiritual interpretations are inherently attached to life’s experiences, whether favorable or adverse—consequently reinforcing the appeal and spread of Pentecostal beliefs

Cephas N. Omenyo observes that Africans demonstrate a remarkable adaptability and openness to new religious movements, particularly when such movements are perceived as capable of addressing their immediate material or spiritual needs.¹¹⁸ This tendency toward religious receptivity is further evidenced by the findings of Chijama Ogbu, who references a global

¹¹³ P. Forum on Religion and Public Life, *Global Christianity: A report on the size and distribution of the World Christian Population*, 2011, p 67

¹¹⁴ D. B. Barrett, “*Annual Statistical Table on Global Mission*”, (Regent University, Virginia Beach, Virginia, 2003) 23

¹¹⁵ V. Synan, *The Magazine: The world growth at 19 million a year*, Nov 1998

¹¹⁶ Barrett, *Annual Statistical Table on Global Mission*, 24-25

¹¹⁷ H. Cox, “*Some personal Reflections on Pentecostalism*”, (Pneuma Publishing Ltd, Lagos Nigeria, 1993),39-44

¹¹⁸ D. Westerlund, *Global Pentecostalism: Encounter with Other Religious Tradition*, (I.B Tauris & Co Ltd, 2009), 57

survey published in *The Citizen Newspaper*.¹¹⁹ According to the survey, Nigeria ranks as the second most religious country in the world, with approximately 83% of its population affirming belief in religion.¹²⁰ Ghana, with 96% of respondents expressing religious affiliation, occupies the first position. The survey, conducted between November 2011 and January 2012, involved interviews with over 52,000 individuals across 57 countries spanning five continents.¹²¹ A.C. Leonard encapsulates the pervasive religiosity of African societies by stating:

*“They are, in the strict and natural sense of the word, a firmly and deeply religious people, of whom it can be said... they eat religiously, dress religiously, and sin religiously. In a few words, the religion of this native... is their existence, and their existence is their religion.”*¹²²

Given such deep-rooted religiosity, it would be reasonable to expect that a nation such as Nigeria—with its fervent commitment to religious life—would exhibit unity along religious lines. Ideally, the Christian Church, particularly within the Pentecostal tradition, would reflect the biblical ideal of one body united in faith and purpose. However, in practice, this is far from reality. Disunity is a persistent issue among Churches in Nigeria, especially within the Pentecostal movement. This fragmentation has contributed to the proliferation of Churches across towns and cities, with many congregations operating independently and often in competition with one another. Some Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria distinguish themselves by emphasizing their spiritual superiority, financial resources, large followings, or purported ability to perform extraordinary miracles. Others have evolved into quasi-family enterprises, where ownership and leadership succession are treated as familial inheritance. In such cases, upon the founder’s death, leadership is typically assumed by the spouse or children, with the family exerting control over Church assets and direction. This trend highlights a deviation from the biblical model of collective leadership and spiritual unity.

¹¹⁹ C. Ogibu, “Survey is contained in an article Religious population” Chijama City Newspaper 13 August 2012

¹²⁰ O. Adetayo, “Global Index of Religiosity and Atheism” (Gallop International 2012) 2

¹²¹ O. Adetayo, “Global Index of Religiosity and Atheism” (Gallop International 2012) 2

¹²² A. Leonard, *The Lower Niger and Its Tribe*, (London: Frank Class, 1968) 29

This fragmentation and personalization of Pentecostalism may be better understood through the lens of hybridization, as argued by scholars such as Ukpong.¹²³ He suggests that Pentecostalism in Nigeria often embodies a hybrid form, merging elements of African Traditional Religion (ATR) with Christian doctrine.¹²⁴ Birgit Meyer reinforces this view by linking Pentecostalism to the neoliberal framework of global capitalism, where religious practice aligns with market-driven ideologies. Such perspectives are compelling. Many Nigerians turn to Pentecostal Churches not solely for communion with God, but to access supernatural interventions for their everyday struggles. Ukah and McCain argue that Pentecostalism, in this context, has assumed the functional role once held by ATR.¹²⁵ In traditional settings, individuals sought solutions to personal and communal crises through sacrifices or rituals administered by local priests—who would often request offerings such as animals, money, or food items to appease the spirits. Pentecostalism, especially through the prosperity gospel, has recontextualized this transactional spiritualism within Christian doctrine, offering promises of divine intervention, healing, and prosperity in exchange for financial "seeds" or sacrificial giving.

This convergence of ATR and Pentecostal Christianity underscores a critical dynamic in Nigerian religious life: while traditional forms of spiritual mediation may have been rebranded, the fundamental expectations from religious institutions—healing, protection, and prosperity—remain deeply entrenched. Consequently, any discourse on Pentecostalism in Nigeria must account for these socio-religious continuities and the implications they hold for Church unity, theological purity, and national development.

¹²³ D. P. Ukpong, *The presence and impact of Pentecostalism in Nigeria*. Posted online at www.glopent.net/.../presence-and-impact-of-pentecostalism-in-Nigeria 2006

¹²⁴ B. Meyer. Pentecostalism and Neo-Liberal Capitalism: Faith, Prosperity and Vision in African Pentecostal-Charismatic Churches. *Journal for the Study of Religion*, Vol. 20, no. 2. DOI: 10.4314/jsr.v20i2.47769, 2007

¹²⁵ A. Ukah. African Christianity: Features, Promises and Problems. Department of Anthropology and African Studies <https://researchgate.net/publication/45667178> Retrieved 12-10-2018, 2007

Max Weber's seminal thesis on the *Protestant work ethic* provides a useful lens through which the ethos of contemporary Pentecostal Churches can be examined, particularly their emphasis on diligence, frugality, entrepreneurial success, and material prosperity.¹²⁶ Scholars have often drawn parallels between Weber's sociological insights and the economic narratives embedded in modern Pentecostalism, especially within the global South. Pentecostalism, in this context, is interpreted by some as a vessel for the transmission of neoliberal capitalist ideologies into developing countries such as Nigeria.¹²⁷ Within this framework, the individual becomes the focal point of success: an autonomous agent, a productive economic being who must demonstrate industriousness, competence, strategic investment, and prudent resource management. Consequently, interrogating the historical development of Pentecostalism in Nigeria becomes imperative for understanding the ideological mechanisms and operational dynamics of its contemporary expressions.¹²⁸

Scholars such as Asonzeh Ukah and David McCain observe that the evolution of Pentecostalism in Nigeria cannot be separated from the broader trajectory of Pentecostal movements across the African continent. The historical roots of Nigerian Pentecostalism have been explored extensively by religious historians and anthropologists alike. For example, Ogbu Kalu situates its origins between the 1910s and 1920s, during which a breakaway from the Anglican Communion led to the establishment of the Christ Army Church (CAC).¹²⁹ This movement gained momentum particularly in southwestern Nigeria amidst the influenza pandemic,¹³⁰ giving rise to new prayer groups and subsequently institutionalised Churches such

¹²⁶ M. Weber, *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*. E-library Edition London: Routledge Classic. 2005

¹²⁷ D. Freeman, *Pentecostalism and Development Churches, NGOs and Social Change in Africa* Ed. New York: Palgrave Macmillan. 2012

¹²⁸ A. Ukah, *Advertising God: "Nigerian Christian Video-Films and the Power of Consumer Culture"* Journal of Religion in Africa Vol. 33, Fasc. 2, 203-231. 2003

¹²⁹ O. Kalu, *African Pentecostalism: An Introduction*. New York: Oxford University Press. 2008

¹³⁰ H. R. Kitause and H. C. Achunike, *"The Future of Prosperity Gospel in Nigeria"*. Quest Journals Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science, Volume 3. Issue 7, 2015, 21-27

as the Christ Apostolic Church, Assemblies of God Church, and the Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel).¹³¹

Ukah proposes a tripartite historical framework for understanding the Nigerian Pentecostal experience:

1. **Classical Pentecostalism**, which emerged in 1914 through the revivalist activities of Garrick Sokari Braide. Braide's ministry was marked by faith healing, prophecy, exorcism, glossolalia (speaking in tongues), spontaneous prayer, and visionary experiences. Although his life and ministry were short-lived, his followers continued his legacy by organising into formal Church structures.
2. **Indigenous or Independent Pentecostalism** developed between the 1920s and 1960s. This phase was characterised by Churches with African origins and leadership, including the Aladura movement, the Apostolic Faith Church (founded by Timothy Gbadebo Oshokoya in 1944), and the Redeemed Christian Church of God (established in 1952).
3. **Neo-Pentecostalism or New Pentecostal Churches** arose in the 1970s. These Churches introduced a distinctive emphasis on personal salvation ("born again" experience), speaking in tongues as a mark of spiritual rebirth, and a theology of prosperity. Institutions such as the Deeper Life Bible Church, Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel), and the Full Gospel Businessmen's Fellowship International belong to this category.¹³²

¹³¹ Pew Research Center, "*Religion and Public Life, The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections*", 2010-2050, 2015.

¹³² A. Ukah, *African Christianity: Features, Promises and Problems*. Department of Anthropology and African Studies, 2007. <https://researchgate.net/publication/45667178> Retrieved 12-10-2018

However, according to Ojo, it shows evidence of British influence in Nigerian Pentecostalism.

¹³³ In further delineating this progression, McCain's *The Metamorphosis of Nigerian Pentecostalism* suggests a slightly different yet complementary model consisting of three waves:

- a) The **first wave** comprises the indigenous revivalist movements of the early 20th century;
- b) The **second wave** involves the transnationalisation of Pentecostalism through the intervention of international missionary networks that supported local revivalist initiatives;
- c) The **third wave**, commencing in the 1970s, was characterised by the widespread Pentecostal revivals among Nigerian university students.¹³⁴

This third wave is particularly significant due to the exposure of indigenous Christian leaders to global Pentecostal influences via pastoral exchange, literature, recorded sermons, and overseas theological training. This cross-pollination of ideas contributed to a hybridised religious expression that retained African spiritual idioms while incorporating global evangelical motifs.

The trajectory of Pentecostalism in Nigeria was neither linear nor uncontested. Its early stages were met with resistance from both colonial ecclesiastical authorities and the dominant mainline Churches, especially the Roman Catholic and Anglican hierarchies. The new movement, often dismissed and marginalised, was pejoratively referred to as *Ijo Elekun* (the "weeping Church")—a reflection of its emotional expressiveness and perceived social marginality. This derision underscored the deep-seated loyalty many Nigerians had toward historic mission Churches, which were often the religious institutions into which they had been

¹³³ M. A. Ojo, "Consonance and Dissonance in the Doctrinal Emphasis of Prosperity among Nigerian Pentecostal" in *African Journal of Pentecostal and Charismatic Studies (AJPCS)*, Vol.1, No.1, February 2013, .9-22

¹³⁴ D. McCain, *The Metamorphosis of Nigerian Pentecostalism. From Signs and Wonders in the Church to Service and Influence in Society*. 2013. In Miller. D. E., Sargeant, K.H., and Flory, R. (Eds.), *Spirit and Power. The Growth and Global Impact of Pentecostalism*. New York: Oxford University Press 2013

born and socialised. Despite these early setbacks, the Pentecostal movement gradually gained momentum, particularly through youth and student involvement. Influential scholars such as J.D.Y. Peel, Matthews A. Ojo, and Ruth Marshall-Fratani have documented this evolution.¹³⁵ Peel's scholarship focuses on the precursors of Pentecostalism, particularly the Aladura movement, while Ojo and Marshall-Fratani examine the multifaceted socio-political implications of Pentecostal growth in Nigeria.

A key turning point in the spread of Pentecostalism was the rise of student-led evangelical revivals in the 1960s and 1970s. Movements such as the Student Christian Movement (SCM), Christian Union (CU), and the Scripture Union (SU) became crucibles for Pentecostal fervour. These groups not only cultivated spiritual discipline among young Nigerians but also acted as incubators for future Pentecostal leaders. Notably, W.F. Kumuyi, founder of Deeper Life Bible Church, was a product of this revivalist wave. The university campuses provided fertile ground for Pentecostal expansion, especially as they were viewed as bastions of light and moral fortitude against the backdrop of rising occult and confraternity activities, including the Pirate Confraternity, Buccaneers, Neo-Black Movement, and others that plagued student life.

The growth of Pentecostalism in Nigeria is best understood as a complex, multi-phase phenomenon shaped by indigenous religious innovation, external missionary influences, sociopolitical factors, and youth engagement. Its doctrinal emphasis on personal salvation, prosperity, and spiritual gifts aligns in many ways with Weberian notions of economic individualism, while simultaneously reflecting the unique historical and cultural contexts of Nigerian society. This layered evolution necessitates a nuanced scholarly engagement with both historical antecedents and contemporary practices of Pentecostal Christianity in Nigeria.

¹³⁵ J. D Peel, Matthews. A. Ojo, *The End-Time Army: Charismatic Movement in Modern Nigeria*, (Africa World Press, Inc, Trenton, NJ USA, 2006), and Ruth Marshall, *Political Spirituality: The Pentecostal Revolution*, The University of Chicago Press Ltd 2009

One school of thought argues that the influence of students who had undergone the baptism of the Holy Spirit played a pivotal role in shaping the Pentecostal movement in Nigeria. These students, drawn from diverse Christian fellowships within tertiary institutions across the country, carried their spiritual experiences back to their home congregations—typically mainline denominations such as the Anglican, Methodist, Baptist, and Evangelical Churches of West Africa. Upon returning, they began to integrate charismatic expressions—such as speaking in tongues, spontaneous prayer, and divine healing—into existing prayer groups within their Churches. This phenomenon catalyzed the emergence of the charismatic movement within Nigeria’s Protestant Churches.

In parallel, the Roman Catholic Church experienced its own charismatic revival, which is believed to have originated in Southwestern Nigeria in 1971 within the Dominican Brotherhood Community. This, according to another school of thought, had far-reaching implications for the wider Nigerian Church. It not only facilitated the gradual acceptance of Pentecostal doctrines across denominations but also contributed to the blurring of doctrinal boundaries between Pentecostal and non-Pentecostal Christian traditions.

Musa Gaiya highlights the significance of Nigerian Pentecostalism in the 1990s, noting its rise as a formidable force in public life.¹³⁶ During this period, Nigeria was grappling with severe socio-economic and political challenges, which had decimated the middle class. As a result, a significant number of middle- and working-class Christians began to abandon mainline Churches in favor of Pentecostal congregations that promised material breakthrough, healing, and solutions to everyday problems through the prosperity gospel and miraculous interventions.¹³⁷ Prominent Pentecostal Churches such as the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) and Mountain of Fire and Miracles Ministries (MFM) strategically expanded

¹³⁶ A. B. Musa “*The Pentecostal revolution in Nigeria*” 2002,1.

¹³⁷ A. B. Musa “*The Pentecostal revolution in Nigeria*” 2002,1.

their operations by acquiring vast lands along the Lagos-Ibadan expressway for evangelism and spiritual retreats. Similarly, the Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel) established a camp in Ajebo, Obafemi / Owode Local Government Area of Ogun State, while Bishop David Oyedepo's Living Faith Church (also known as Winners' Chapel) relocated its headquarters from Kaduna to Otta in Ogun State, further solidifying the physical and symbolic presence of Pentecostalism in southern Nigeria.

Allan Anderson offers a broader cultural explanation for the rapid spread of Pentecostalism across Africa in the 20th century.¹³⁸ He suggests that part of its success lies in its alignment with indigenous African modes of religious expression. Pentecostalism, like African Christianity more generally, heavily relies on oral structures—such as narrative theology, oral liturgies, testimonies, and communal participation in worship. These practices resonate deeply with African traditions that value storytelling, visions, dreams, and holistic healing rituals involving prayer and liturgical dance.¹³⁹ Anderson, along with Walter Hollenweger, further notes that the dynamism and spontaneity characteristic of Pentecostal worship do not negate liturgy; rather, they foster flexible, orally transmitted liturgical forms memorized and enacted by the congregation.¹⁴⁰ A crucial feature of this worship style is the active participation of all members, reinforcing a sense of collective empowerment and spiritual agency.

This participatory approach stands in contrast to the more hierarchical and centralized worship structures typical of mainline Churches. The World Council of Churches, in its affirmation statement, supports such an inclusive model, advocating for a paradigm shift—from viewing the Church solely as a steward of the earth to recognizing its role in strengthening the spiritual and social fabric of both households and communities. This model encourages individual

¹³⁸ A. H. Anderson & W.J. Hollenweger, *Pentecostal After a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition*, (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999) 23.

¹³⁹ Ibid

¹⁴⁰ A. H. Anderson & W..J. Hollenweger, *Pentecostal After a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition*, (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999)

responsibility, active engagement, and collective upliftment, principles that resonate strongly with Pentecostal ecclesiology and practice.¹⁴¹

2.8 The Expansion of Pentecostalism in Southwest Nigeria

According to Obiora (1998), the proliferation of Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria has reached unprecedented levels, likened metaphorically to the spontaneous multiplication of maggots.¹⁴² These Churches are rapidly emerging across virtually every locality in the nation, with the southwestern region—comprising cities like Lagos, Ibadan, and Akure—experiencing the most concentrated growth.¹⁴³ The number of Churches and prayer houses belonging to the Pentecostal tradition is simply overwhelming.¹⁴⁴ As of 1998, the total number of Pentecostal Churches in just these three urban centres was reported to be 1,018.¹⁴⁵ Furthermore, *Christian Today*, an online Christian publication, estimated in 2007 that Nigeria had approximately 3.9 million Pentecostal Churches. Given the exponential growth rate of the movement, it is reasonable to assume that this number has significantly increased over the past decade and a half.

This dramatic surge in Pentecostal establishments has attracted scholarly interest, particularly in relation to its socio-economic and developmental implications. The visible clustering of Pentecostal Churches within residential and commercial zones has raised critical questions. As Omeh (n.d.) observes, it is not uncommon to find as many as ten to fifteen different Pentecostal denominations co-existing along a single street, with some even occupying separate units within the same building.¹⁴⁶ Such spatial saturation is reflective not only of the movement's

¹⁴¹ "The Gospel and African Religion," The Free Library, 2000 World Council of Churches 22 Mar. 2022

¹⁴² F. K. Obiora, *The Divine Deceit: Business in Religion*. Enugu: Optimal. 1998

¹⁴³ F. K. Obiora, *The Divine Deceit: Business in Religion*. Enugu: Optimal. 1998

¹⁴⁴ W. C. Ihejirika, *An Audience Ethnography on the Role of the Mass Media in the Process of Conversion of Catholics to the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria*. Roma: Pontificia Universita Gregoriana. 2004

¹⁴⁵ Christian Today online magazine

¹⁴⁶ C. Omeh, Oral Interview on Pentecostalism in Nigeria. 2016

rapid expansion but also of the deep spiritual and existential anxieties permeating Nigerian society.¹⁴⁷

The persistence of socio-political instability and economic hardships since Nigeria's independence in 1960—characterised by poverty, hunger, disease, unemployment, exploitation, and political repression—has created fertile ground for religious expression and expansion. In this context, religion serves as both a coping mechanism and a medium for seeking divine intervention in the affairs of daily life. Nigerians have historically turned to spiritual institutions in times of crisis, and the sustained growth of Pentecostalism appears intricately linked to this reality. Indeed, more than six decades after independence, Pentecostal Christianity remains one of the most consistently expanding religious sectors in the country.

The Nigerian Constitution, though affirming the secular nature of the state, strongly upholds the right to freedom of religion. Section 38(1) of the 1999 Constitution (as amended) guarantees every citizen the liberty to manifest and propagate their faith in worship, teaching, and practice. This constitutional provision not only legitimises the pervasive religious activities in the country but also reflects the deep-seated religious consciousness of its people. For most Nigerians, religion represents a vital portal through which the supernatural is invited into human experience.

During periods of military rule, particularly in the 1980s and 1990s, the Church—especially Pentecostal congregations—played a critical role in resisting authoritarianism and providing moral leadership. Churches became safe havens where citizens sought divine deliverance from the oppressive political climate. Pentecostal leaders were especially vocal in framing Nigeria's political struggles as spiritual warfare, calling for national deliverance from "satanic strongholds" that impeded progress. These movements were instrumental in raising political

¹⁴⁷ D. Olatunji, Oral Interview on Pentecostalism in Nigeria, 2016

and spiritual consciousness among the populace and in preserving social order during a time of economic and psychological distress.

Paradoxically, while Pentecostal Churches have continued to grow in number and influence, there has also been a steady rise in the national crime rate. This troubling parallel suggests that the expansion of religious institutions has not necessarily translated into moral or societal transformation. In Lagos State, for instance, some scholars have noted that the growth of Pentecostalism mirrors the increasing incidence of crime, raising concerns about the depth of spiritual conversion and the societal impact of these religious movements.¹⁴⁸

The Pentecostal revival that gained momentum in the 1980s in Lagos began as a vision-driven movement, aiming to cultivate a new breed of faithful Christians capable of national transformation. Early teachings were anchored in themes of personal holiness, sanctification, and moral uprightness. However, by the late 1990s, a significant theological shift occurred. Emphasis began to move away from ascetic Christian values toward doctrines of prosperity, healing, and emotional wellness. This new wave of Pentecostalism mirrors the socio-economic aspirations of many Nigerians, particularly in the face of widespread economic insecurity.

Consequently, contemporary Pentecostal messages now resonate with the ideals of restoration, wealth acquisition, and familial stability—benefits now interpreted as the earthly manifestations of the Kingdom of God. This paradigm shift has, to a significant extent, blurred the once-clear boundaries between Pentecostal and mainline denominations. In practice, many Pentecostal Churches have adopted theological and liturgical elements that align closely with those of more traditional Christian bodies.

In essence, the religiosity of Nigerians is not in question. What remains problematic is the transformative power of religion in shaping ethical conduct and public morality. As the

¹⁴⁸ Akpeli .O. Andrew: *Explaining the Spread of Pentecostalism in Nigeria*, 22 May 2012

celebrated Nigerian author Onuorah Nzekwu (year) poignantly critiques, many Churches have become centres of self-serving spiritual theatrics rather than agents of profound moral and societal renewal. This critique underscores the growing disillusionment with religious institutions that appear to prioritise institutional expansion and prosperity preaching over genuine spiritual regeneration. There is a growing sentiment among critics and concerned observers that the Nigerian Church, particularly the Pentecostal movement, has not fulfilled its moral and social responsibility to the nation. As one critic poignantly noted,

*"The Churches have failed this nation. I don't think there is any nation in the world that has the same number of Churches as Nigeria. But, unfortunately, the more the Churches multiplied, the eviler we become."*¹⁴⁹

This statement encapsulates the paradox that characterises the Nigerian religious landscape—an environment where spiritual proliferation does not necessarily equate to societal transformation. Indeed, Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria have become a microcosm of the larger society—an amalgamation of virtue and vice, integrity and corruption. They reflect the broader structural contradictions and socio-political tensions that define the Nigerian state. This is particularly evident in the Southwest region, where the growth and diversification of Pentecostalism mirror the deeply entrenched divisions in the Nigerian social fabric. A school of thought argues that the disunity within Pentecostalism is a direct reflection of the disunity within Nigerian society itself, underscoring the influence of societal fragmentation on ecclesiastical relationships.

One striking dimension of contemporary Pentecostalism in Nigeria is the distinctive style and comportment of its clergy. Nigerian Pentecostal pastors, especially those operating in metropolitan hubs like Lagos, have adopted highly sophisticated methods of self-presentation. Their modes of communication, linguistic flair, phonetic precision, sartorial elegance, and

¹⁴⁹ O. Nzekwu, *Excerpt from an interview he granted Mathew Irekiigbe*, (The Sun Newspaper, Saturday, July 26, 2003). P4

charisma present them as paragons of modernity and cosmopolitanism. Reuben Abati captures this phenomenon succinctly when he describes the new-age Nigerian pastor as

The new generation Pastor is a spellbinder; he dresses well, he rides very flashy cars, he even carries a gun, just in case; he is a part-time businessman. He doesn't need to have attended any Bible College, as long as he can quote passages from the Bible and report to a bewildered congregation about what his Daddy (God) told him in the night, he would get a captive audience.¹⁵⁰

These pastors are often compelling orators with an uncanny ability to connect with diverse audiences. Many are alumni of Nigerian tertiary institutions, possessing robust academic credentials which they have successfully repurposed for ministerial use. Their educational background equips them with the tools necessary to thrive in an environment where literacy remains a challenge for many, yet intellectual sophistication is highly admired. Consequently, their academic exposure, global awareness, and personal ambitions play a significant role in shaping their pastoral vision and strategic direction. The leadership style of each Church, therefore, is heavily influenced by the personality and aspirations of its founder or presiding pastor. Previous scholarship on Pentecostalism in Nigeria has largely focused on the origins of the movement, its theological distinctions from mainline Churches, its socio-economic entanglements, and the widespread popularity of the prosperity gospel. While these studies have significantly enriched our understanding of Nigerian Pentecostalism, there remains a critical gap in the literature regarding intra-Pentecostal relations and the persistent issue of fragmentation within the movement—especially in Southwest Nigeria where Pentecostalism has found deep roots.

This study addresses that gap by shifting the focus from origin and growth to the imperative of unity. It explores the factors contributing to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in the Southwest, with particular attention to Lagos—the commercial capital of Nigeria and the epicentre of Pentecostal influence. Lagos hosts the headquarters of several prominent

¹⁵⁰A. Reuben: “*Rape & the Senior Pastor of COZA*”. Newsdairy July 2, 2019.

Pentecostal denominations and serves as a fertile ground for both cooperation and conflict within the movement. Through a critical engagement with existing scholarship, fieldwork, and contextual analysis, this study seeks to propose practical and theological pathways toward fostering unity and collaboration among Pentecostal Churches in this pivotal region

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is grounded in the pragmatist philosophical paradigm, which offers a flexible and integrative framework well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena. From an ontological standpoint, pragmatism acknowledges that reality is both singular and multiple—existing independently while simultaneously shaped by human experiences and interpretations. Epistemologically, the pragmatist paradigm challenges the rigid dichotomy between positivism and interpretivism. It rejects the exclusive pursuit of either wholly objective truths or entirely subjective meanings, instead advocating for a context-driven, practical, and action-oriented approach to knowledge generation.

The adoption of this paradigm in the present study reflects the researcher's recognition that perceptions of reality are situational and dynamic, particularly within socially and spiritually nuanced environments such as Pentecostal communities. Given the multiplicity of views and lived experiences within these Churches, the study embraced a pluralistic epistemology, allowing for both objective measurements and subjective interpretations.

Accordingly, a mixed-methods research design was employed, combining quantitative methods—to capture generalizable trends—and qualitative techniques—to delve into the deeper, context-specific meanings attributed to Church disunity. This methodological integration not only ensured greater breadth and depth in the data analysis but also aligned with the core tenets of pragmatism: to produce knowledge that is both analytically robust and practically relevant. By adopting this approach, the study was able to yield nuanced, evidence-based insights into the multifactorial causes of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria, with a specific focus on Lagos State.

3.1 Research Design

The study employed a descriptive survey research design aimed at systematic fact-finding and the objective presentation of observable phenomena. As previously indicated, a mixed-methods approach was adopted to enhance the depth and reliability of the data collected. The quantitative component involved the administration of structured questionnaires designed to capture measurable responses across a wide participant base. This was complemented by the qualitative component, which consisted of unstructured interviews conducted through various channels, including telephone conversations, social media messaging platforms, and email correspondence.

The integration of both quantitative and qualitative methods provided a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. The descriptive approach was particularly instrumental in enabling the researcher to analyze patterns, summarize participant perspectives, and draw meaningful inferences from the data. This methodological framework not only facilitated the effective presentation of results but also supported the formulation of evidence-based recommendations aligned with the study's objectives and findings.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this research consisted of members and clergy drawn from four major Pentecostal denominations in Nigeria, namely: the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC), Mountain of Fire and Miracles Ministries (MFM), and the Living Faith Church (Winners Chapel). These Churches were selected due to their national prominence, expansive membership base, and significant influence on the religious landscape of contemporary Nigerian Pentecostalism.

A total of 1,000 individuals were considered for this study, encompassing both lay congregants and ordained ministers. This diverse respondent pool was deliberately chosen to ensure a

comprehensive representation of perspectives across various levels of Church hierarchy and participation. Including both leaders and followers provides a balanced understanding of theological beliefs, worship practices, and socio-cultural dynamics within these Pentecostal movements, thereby enriching the overall validity and depth of the research findings.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Technique

This research adopted a mixed sampling strategy, combining both purposive and simple random sampling techniques to ensure the representativeness and relevance of the study population. Purposive sampling was strategically employed to select key worship centres, specifically targeting the hierarchical structures within the selected Churches, including Parishes, Area Headquarters, Zonal Headquarters, Provincial Headquarters, District Headquarters, and Regional and State Headquarters. The rationale behind this approach was to capture a broad spectrum of perspectives and practices that are often shaped by organizational status and administrative significance within the ecclesiastical framework.

Following the purposive identification of these pivotal worship centres, the study proceeded with the use of simple random sampling to select a total of 1,000 respondents. This phase of the sampling process was conducted without consideration of predefined demographic or social variables, thereby minimizing selection bias and ensuring that each individual within the selected locations had an equal probability of being included in the sample. By integrating purposive and random techniques, the research ensured both depth and breadth in respondent selection, enhancing the validity and generalizability of the findings across the different strata of the Church organizational structure.

3.4 Instrumentation

The primary research instrument utilized in this study was a structured questionnaire, meticulously designed and developed by the researcher. Prior to its administration, the

instrument underwent a rigorous validation process to ensure its reliability and content validity. This tool, titled the *Ecumenism Rating Scale (ERS)*, was specifically constructed to align with the study's objectives and to facilitate the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data.

The ERS was divided into two main sections. Section A was dedicated to capturing essential demographic data from the respondents, such as age, gender, educational background, denominational affiliation, and years of religious involvement. This demographic information provided a contextual framework for interpreting the participants' responses. Section B of the instrument consisted of fifty (50) carefully constructed items, with ten (10) items corresponding to each of the five core research questions. These items were designed to elicit respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and experiences related to the theme of ecumenism within the religious context under investigation. Each item in Section B was presented using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," allowing for the measurement of varying degrees of agreement or disagreement.

The design of the ERS was guided by both theoretical constructs and empirical considerations to ensure that it effectively captured the nuances of ecumenical attitudes and practices. This instrument served as a critical data collection tool in examining the patterns, challenges, and opportunities associated with ecumenism as perceived by the study's target population.

3.5 Administration of Instruments

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection process for this study was systematically designed to ensure broad representation across the selected Pentecostal denominations. A total of 1,000 structured questionnaires were evenly distributed among four prominent Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria—The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC), Mountain of Fire and Miracles Ministries (MFM), and Living Faith Church (also

known as Winners Chapel)—with each denomination receiving 250 copies. Of the distributed questionnaires, 820 were duly completed and returned, yielding a high response rate of 82%.

The questionnaire utilized a standardized 5-point Likert scale, allowing respondents to express their level of agreement or disagreement with various statements across a continuum of response options. This format was selected to capture nuanced perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to the study's thematic focus. In addition to the quantitative data gathered through the questionnaires, qualitative insights were obtained via interviews conducted with 80 selected participants—20 from each of the aforementioned Churches. These interviews were carried out using a mixed approach: some were conducted in person, while others were held remotely via telephone, depending on the participants' availability and location.

Altogether, data were collected from 900 individuals, combining both survey and interview respondents. This comprehensive dataset provided a robust empirical foundation for the analysis and interpretation of findings in the present research.

3.6 Data Analysis

The process of data analysis was systematically aligned with the nature and structure of the data collected, ensuring methodological rigour and relevance. Both quantitative and qualitative datasets were subjected to appropriate analytical procedures using standard digital tools, including Microsoft Excel for statistical and numerical data handling, and Microsoft Word for organizing and interpreting open-ended, textual responses. The analytical framework involved a series of methodical steps: responses were initially sorted and categorized, followed by the assignment of numerical or alphanumeric codes to facilitate structured interpretation. While some responses required detailed coding schemes to extract underlying themes or patterns, others were directly tabulated based on predefined response options selected by participants. This structured approach ensured consistency and reliability across all research questions.

Subsequent to classification and coding, the data were systematically inputted into a statistical analysis matrix. This enabled the exploration of relationships between key variables, group comparisons, and evaluation of interdependent effects. The structured data analysis provided a robust basis for interpreting trends, drawing inferences, and supporting the overarching research objectives.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Research Findings

To ensure the successful completion of this doctoral research, a comprehensive and critical analysis of the data obtained through the formulated research questions is imperative. As detailed in the preceding chapter, the data was collected using instruments based on the Likert scale format, allowing for structured responses that reflect varying degrees of agreement or perception. This chapter is dedicated to presenting the empirical data gathered during the research process. It proceeds with a systematic and rigorous examination of the responses, offering a detailed interpretation of the findings in light of the study's objectives. Through this analytical process, key patterns, trends, and implications are identified, providing a robust foundation for drawing meaningful conclusions and supporting the overall research narrative.

4.1.1 Questionnaire Analysis

A total of 1,000 structured questionnaires were distributed as part of the data collection process for this study. Out of these, 820 fully completed and valid responses were successfully retrieved and subsequently utilized for the quantitative analysis. During the initial data screening and validation phase, 180 responses were excluded from the final dataset due to various inconsistencies. Specifically, 95 questionnaires were disqualified due to the presence of multiple conflicting responses to single-answer questions, 58 were excluded as a result of significant omissions or incomplete data, and 27 respondents were removed on the basis of lacking sufficient knowledge or understanding of Pentecostalism and its contextual relevance to the study. These exclusions were essential in maintaining the integrity, reliability, and validity of the research findings.

In addition to the questionnaire data, 80 responses were obtained through semi-structured interviews conducted with key informants. These interviews provided qualitative insights that complemented the quantitative data and enhanced the overall depth of analysis.

The valid quantitative responses ($n = 820$) were subjected to frequency distribution analysis. This involved aggregating and categorizing the participants' answers to each question in order to identify patterns and determine the most frequently occurring responses. The resulting frequencies were subsequently converted into percentage representations and organized within structured tables to facilitate interpretation.

The researcher employed a combination of univariate and multivariate tables, depending on the nature of the variables under examination. In some cases, multiple variables were consolidated within a single table to allow for comparative analysis. The primary objective of the research was to investigate the issue of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. As part of the data refinement and cleaning process, responses from participants who demonstrated an evident lack of comprehension regarding the concept of disunity within Pentecostal contexts were systematically excluded. This methodological decision was made to ensure the credibility and robustness of the study's findings, given the research's central aim of identifying practical and contextually appropriate solutions to the challenges of disunity within the Pentecostal movement in the region. The final presentation of findings is summarized in the tables below, with up to 900 cumulative responses displayed, depending on the validity and completeness of responses across various sections of the questionnaire instrument.

Research Question 1

To what extent is unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria regarded as important in accordance with biblical teachings?

Table 1: Respondents' Views on the Importance of Unity Among Pentecostal Churches

S/N	Items	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	There is nothing like unity	715	79.4	185	20.6
2.	In unity, the Churches can stand	701	77.9	199	22.1
3.	No meaningful thing can be achieved without unity	711	79.0	189	21.0
4.	When there is unity there is progress	748	83.1	152	16.9
5.	Even God may not break the cord of unity easily	633	70.3	267	29.7
6.	All enemy efforts are useless when there is unity	635	70.6	265	29.4
7.	The Church may work together toward unity	600	66.7	300	33.3
8.	Jesus' earnest prayer is that the Church be made one and unite	768	85.3	132	14.7
9.	Prayer may be important to the Church's unity	574	63.8	326	36.2
10.	Programmes toward unity are encouraged for the Churches	715	79.4	185	20.6
	TOTAL	6,800		2,200	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 above

Total number of respondents that agreed = 6,800

Total number of respondents that disagreed = 2,200

Grand Total number of respondents = 6,800 + 2,200 = 9,000

Percentage of respondents that agreed = $6800 / 9000 \times 100 = 75.6\%$

Percentage of respondents that disagreed = $2200 / 9000 \times 100 = 24.4\%$

Interpretation and Analysis

The data presented in Table 1 provide compelling insight into the collective perspective of respondents regarding the importance of unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria, especially in relation to biblical teachings. A significant proportion of respondents consistently affirmed the value of unity across various dimensions. Notably, 85.3% agreed with the assertion that Jesus' earnest prayer was for the Church to be united, directly referencing the biblical passage in John 17:21, which underscores the theological foundation for ecclesiastical unity.

Similarly, strong agreement was recorded on other unity-related statements such as "When there is unity, there is progress" (83.1%), and "There is nothing like unity" (79.4%). These responses reflect a widespread acknowledgment of the role unity plays in fostering spiritual growth, resilience against external opposition, and progress within Church structures. The statement, "No meaningful thing can be achieved without unity," affirmed by 79% of respondents, further illustrates the functional and missional importance attributed to unity.

Though slightly lower in agreement, items such as "Prayer may be important to the Church's unity" (63.8%) and "The Church may work together toward unity" (66.7%) suggest that while the theological foundation of unity is widely accepted, practical implementation through spiritual disciplines and cooperative efforts may face certain challenges or varying levels of commitment.

Overall, the overwhelming support for unity as a biblical and strategic imperative among Pentecostal Churches affirms its critical role in the religious, social, and organizational life of the Church in the region. These findings not only align with core Christian teachings but also highlight the need for intentional initiatives that promote and sustain unity among diverse congregations.

Research Question 2

To what extent do doctrinal differences contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

Table 2: Respondents' Views on doctrinal differences contribute to disunity.

S/N	Items	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	The Bible teaches the same doctrine	669	74.3	231	25.7
2.	Churches only have problems interpreting the doctrine of the Bible	672	74.7	228	25.3
3.	Doctrine has divided us in the way we handle them	771	85.7	129	14.3
4.	Church leaders are not sincere most times they interpret the bible	752	83.6	148	16.4
5.	Leaders interpret doctrine just to favour themselves	690	76.7	214	23.8
6.	I am of Apollo, I am of Paul is the order of the day now	653	72.6	247	27.4
7.	God uses word standards to checkmate excuses of leaders in self-doctrinal practice	619	68.8	281	31.2
8.	Church leader's involvement in doctrine needs to be dealt with	771	85.7	129	14.3
9.	Pentecostal Churches are more divided among themselves than mainline Churches	612	68.0	284	31.6
10.	God did not give us doctrine to divide us	800	88.9	100	11.1
	TOTAL	7,009		1,991	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 above

Total number of respondents that agreed = 7,009

Total number of respondents that disagreed = 1,991

Grand Total number of respondents = 7009 + 1991 = 9,000

Percentage of respondents that agreed = $7009 / 9000 \times 100 = 77.9\%$

Percentage of respondents that disagreed = $1991 / 9000 \times 100 = 22.1\%$

Interpretation and Analysis of Table 2

Table 2 provides empirical evidence highlighting the extent to which doctrinal differences contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. The responses indicate a strong consensus among participants that doctrinal divergence, particularly in the interpretation and application of biblical teachings, is a significant cause of fragmentation within the Pentecostal movement.

A majority of respondents (above 70% across most items) acknowledged that while the Bible itself presents a unified doctrine, problems arise primarily from inconsistent and often self-serving interpretations by Church leaders. Notably, 85.7% agreed that doctrinal mismanagement has led to division, and the same proportion affirmed the need to address the role of leaders in doctrinal disputes.

Moreover, 83.6% of respondents perceived a lack of sincerity among Church leaders in their handling of doctrinal matters, further reinforcing the argument that leadership behavior—rather than doctrine itself—is a central contributor to disunity. The reference to sectarian tendencies (e.g., “I am of Apollos, I am of Paul”) also reflects a denominational identity crisis within the Pentecostal fold, confirmed by 72.6% agreement.

Interestingly, 88.9% of participants refuted the idea that doctrine was intended by God to divide the Church, indicating a theological consensus that division stems from human factors rather than divine intent.

Ultimately, the analysis of Table 2 reveals that doctrinal differences, particularly as influenced by personal interpretations and leadership interests, significantly fuel disunity among Pentecostal Churches in the region. This highlights a critical need for doctrinal clarity, ethical leadership, and interdenominational dialogue to promote unity and cohesion.

Research Question 3

To what extent does the pursuit of financial supremacy contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

Table 3: Respondents' Views on pursuit of financial supremacy contribute to disunity.

S/N	Items	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	We cannot all belong to the same denomination	769	85.4	131	14.6
2.	Even Jesus recognised another religious group with the same purpose	471	52.3	429	47.7
3.	Not all leaders of Churches are called	755	83.9	145	16.1
4.	Many are in the ministry for food's sake	842	93.6	58	6.4
5.	Most Church programmes are geared towards money making	796	88.4	104	11.6
6.	Serious priority is given to money making than spirituality	726	80.7	174	19.3
7.	Many Pastor are interested in members' pockets rather than their souls	756	84.0	144	16.0
8.	Many evangelised just for the numerical size	615	68.3	285	31.7
9.	Some Pastors do not bother whether members make it to heaven or not	729	81.0	171	19.0
10.	Most leaders need a change of orientation towards money in the Church	733	81.4	167	18.6
	TOTAL	7192		1808	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 above

Total number of respondents that agreed = 7,192

Total number of respondents that disagreed = 1,808

Grand Total number of respondents = 7,192 + 1,808 = 9,000

Percentage of respondents that agreed = $7192 / 9000 \times 100 = 79.9\%$

Percentage of respondents that disagreed = $1808 / 9000 \times 100 = 20.1\%$

Interpretation and Analysis of Table 2

Interpretation and Analysis of Table 3

Table 3 presents respondents' views regarding the influence of financial motivations on the unity and integrity of Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. The data reflects a strong perception that the quest for financial gain has become a central concern in many Pentecostal ministries, often at the expense of spiritual focus and doctrinal unity.

A significant majority of respondents (93.6%) agreed that many individuals have entered ministry primarily "for food's sake," suggesting that financial incentives, rather than divine calling or pastoral passion, are major driving forces for Church leadership. Additionally, 88.4% of respondents asserted that Church programs are increasingly designed with money-making objectives, while 80.7% indicated that material wealth is prioritized over spiritual growth.

Furthermore, 84% agreed that some pastors focus more on members' financial contributions than on their spiritual well-being, reinforcing the perception of a commercialized approach to ministry. The belief that not all Church leaders are genuinely called (83.9%) and that many pastors evangelize merely for numerical expansion (68.3%) suggests a trend toward institutional competitiveness and materialistic rivalry.

Interestingly, while 85.4% of respondents acknowledged the necessity of denominational diversity, the widespread concern over financial motivations points to a deeper issue: disunity rooted not in theological divergence but in competing economic interests. This is further underscored by 81.4% of respondents affirming the need for a reorientation of Church leadership toward a more spiritually grounded vision.

Finally, the analysis of Table 3 reveals that the Pentecostal landscape is increasingly shaped by economic considerations—manifesting in competitive Church programming, leadership opportunism, and membership monetization. While denominational plurality is acknowledged, the disunity observed appears to stem less from doctrinal variation and more from the pursuit of financial dominance among Church leaders.

Research Question 4

To what extent do competition in congregational size, membership growth, and the expansion of worship centres contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

Table 4: Respondents' Views on the extent competition contribute to disunity.

S / N	Items	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	Many boast their congregational size	679	75.4	221	24.6
2.	Many leaders are proud of their worship centre	514	57.1	386	42.9
3.	Many are concerned with membership numbers and not those that will make it to heaven	782	86.9	118	13.1
4.	Some leaders waste a fortune on worship centres rather than on members' welfare	745	82.8	155	17.2
5.	Some evangelise only the rich	685	76.1	215	23.9
6.	Some value their properties more than members' souls	601	66.8	299	33.2
7.	Some leaders consider other leaders' Church size before they are invited	368	40.9	532	59.1
8.	Some leaders look down on other men of God they consider less privilege	764	84.9	136	15.1
9.	There are so many unhealthy rivalries among men of God	730	81.1	170	18.9
10.	Many are too proud of their self-achievement	718	79.8	182	20.2
	TOTAL	6,586		2,414	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 above

Total number of respondents that agreed = 6,586

Total number of respondents that disagreed = 2,414

Grand Total of respondents = 6,586 + 2,414 = 9,000

Percentage of respondents that agreed = $6586 / 9000 \times 100 = 73.2\%$

Percentage of respondents that disagreed = $2414 / 9000 \times 100 = 26.8\%$

Interpretation and Analysis of Table 4

The data in Table 4 offers critical insight into the ways competitive behaviour among Pentecostal Church leaders may contribute to ecclesiastical disunity in Southwest Nigeria. A significant majority of respondents across multiple indicators recognize that Church competition—whether in terms of size, infrastructure, or social status—is a growing concern within the movement.

For instance, 86.9% of respondents believe that many leaders prioritize numerical growth over spiritual formation, suggesting a departure from core evangelical values. Similarly, 82.8% agreed that significant financial resources are directed toward the construction of worship centres, often at the expense of member welfare. This trend reflects a materialistic orientation that may alienate the Church from its social and spiritual responsibilities.

Additionally, over 84% of participants noted that some leaders display condescension toward less affluent clergy, reinforcing hierarchical divisions and undermining collaboration. Unhealthy rivalry was acknowledged by 81.1%, underscoring the extent to which interpersonal and inter-ministerial competition fuels fragmentation.

Although fewer respondents (40.9%) agreed that Church size influences ministerial invitations, the relatively high percentages across other items reinforce the overall perception that pride, materialism, and competition are deeply embedded issues. These factors appear to be major drivers of disunity, posing challenges to the theological and missional integrity of the Pentecostal movement.

As a final observation, the findings in Table 4 strongly suggest that status-driven competition among Pentecostal leaders—particularly in terms of congregational numbers, infrastructure, and personal prestige—constitutes a significant barrier to unity.

Research Question 5:

To what extent are Church leaders unwilling to relinquish doctrinal practices in order to promote unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

Table 5: Respondents' Views Church leaders relinquish doctrinal practices.

S/N	Items	Agreed		Disagreed	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1.	Leaders teach doctrine to divide rather than unite the Church.	386	42.9	514	57.1
2.	Christian Association of Nigeria need to do something in this respect	690	76.7	210	23.3
3.	Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria should do something too	723	80.3	377	41.9
4.	Pride makes it difficult for most Pastors to work with others	691	76.8	159	17.7
5.	Pastors' different interpretations of the Bible make doctrine to be different to members	624	69.3	276	30.7
6.	A superiority complex will not make some Pastors have anything to do with other men of God	660	73.3	239	26.6
7.	A forum to iron out differences among Pentecostal Churches in need	368	40.9	532	59.1
8.	Pastors need to review how they teach doctrine	696	77.3	155	17.2
9.	Doctrines dissemination should not divide Christians	732	81.3	118	13.1
10.	Christians need to adhere to Christ's prayer in John Chapter 17 for the unity of the Church	702	78.0	148	16.4
	TOTAL	6272		2728	

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 above

Total number of respondents that agreed = 6,272

Total number of respondents that disagreed = 2,728

Grand Total of respondents = 6,272 + 2,728 = 9,000

Percentage respondents that agreed = $6272 / 9000 \times 100 = 68.7\%$

Percentage of respondents that disagreed = $2728 / 9000 \times 100 = 30.3\%$

Interpretation and Analysis of Table 5

The data presented in Table 5 sheds light on respondents' perspectives regarding the role of Church leaders in maintaining or relinquishing doctrinal practices for the sake of unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. While a slight majority (57.1%) disagreed that leaders intentionally teach doctrine to divide the Church, a significant number of participants (42.9%) still hold this perception—suggesting a lingering mistrust regarding the motives behind doctrinal instruction.

Notably, a vast majority of respondents agreed that both the Christian Association of Nigeria (76.7%) and the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (80.3%) should play proactive roles in mitigating doctrinal disunity. This indicates a general expectation for institutional intervention to mediate and unify fragmented denominational practices.

Further, 76.8% of respondents attributed disunity to pastoral pride, while 73.3% highlighted a superiority complex as a barrier to inter-Church cooperation. These attitudes were seen as critical obstacles preventing leaders from fostering collaborative relationships. Additionally, the varied interpretation of biblical doctrine by pastors was cited by 69.3% of participants as a cause of confusion and division among Church members.

Interestingly, while 81.3% affirmed that doctrine should not be a dividing tool, and 78.0% emphasized the relevance of Christ's prayer for unity (John 17), a lower proportion (40.9%) agreed on the necessity of creating forums to address doctrinal differences—perhaps reflecting skepticism about the feasibility or sincerity of such initiatives.

Overall, the responses suggest that although Church members and observers overwhelmingly desire unity, they perceive doctrinal rigidity, leadership ego, and institutional inertia as

persistent barriers. Therefore, a shift in doctrinal attitudes, combined with intentional efforts from Church associations and leadership bodies, is essential to promoting cohesion within the Pentecostal movement in the region.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSIONS, SUMMARY, AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Further Discussion of Research Findings

A critical examination of existing research reveals that doctrinal divergence constitutes a principal source of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. As the proliferation of Pentecostal denominations continues to expand across the urban and rural landscapes of the region, so too does the diversity of doctrinal teachings propagated within these congregations. The study's respondents overwhelmingly indicated that this doctrinal plurality has contributed to fragmentation within the Pentecostal movement, undermining any sense of cohesive theological or ecclesial identity.

Beyond doctrinal disparities, the research also identifies financial interests as a significant catalyst for disunity among Pentecostal Churches in the region. According to several participants, the message of prosperity continues to dominate the Pentecostal theological landscape more than in the Mainline Churches. These respondents argued that the pursuit of financial gain by some Pentecostal leaders has led to the commercialization of the faith—a phenomenon colloquially referred to by the researcher as "Pentecostpreneurship," which refers to the strategic establishment of Churches for the primary purpose of economic benefit. This commercialization further fractures ecclesiastical unity, as competition for congregants and financial resources intensifies among various Church founders.

Notably, the study underscores a profound yearning among respondents for ecclesial unity, irrespective of doctrinal distinctions, nomenclature, or denominational identity. Participants articulated a shared desire for a unified body of Christ, aligning with the biblical mandate for unity as expressed in the high priestly prayer of Jesus in John 17:11, where Christ prayed to the Father to make His followers one. This aspiration for unity transcended institutional labels

and emphasized core Christian values such as love, purpose, and the redemptive message of the cross. For many, the authenticity of the Church lies not in its denominational brand, but in its embodiment of Christ's mission—to lead all people, regardless of age or background, toward salvation and spiritual transformation.

The findings further suggest that many respondents envision a united Pentecostal Church as a potent agent of social and national cohesion. Since Church members are integrally embedded within families, communities, and the larger societal fabric, ecclesiastical unity could foster broader societal harmony. Some respondents asserted that Christians, particularly Pentecostals, represent one of the largest socio-religious demographics in Nigeria. Consequently, a unified Pentecostal movement could catalyse national integration and transformation. Participants suggested that if Pentecostal Churches genuinely practiced biblical Christianity—rooted in love and unity—their collective witness would significantly enhance the credibility and effectiveness of organizations such as the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) and, by extension, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN). Such a development could inspire conversions from other religious traditions and foster interfaith harmony within communities.

Moreover, the study reveals that improved inter-Church relations may be facilitated through regular, collaborative initiatives. Respondents recommended that the PFN institutionalize annual nationwide inter-denominational conferences and camp meetings that bring together members from diverse Pentecostal denominations. These gatherings would serve as platforms for shared worship experiences, such as joint Holy Communion services, as well as spiritual and doctrinal enrichment. Respondents also proposed the organization of inter-denominational evangelistic crusades, expos, and outreach programmes across communities, villages, and urban centres. These events would not only promote unity but also reinforce the collective mission of soul-winning.

In addition to spiritual collaboration, the study highlights the potential for joint socio-educational initiatives. Pentecostal Churches could pool their resources to establish mission schools offering free education in underserved areas, staffed by missionaries and trained personnel from participating congregations. However, for such projects to succeed, foundational emphasis must be placed on shared values, unity of purpose, and the evangelistic goal of the Church. These institutions would serve both as instruments of social development and as tools for evangelism, creating a tangible impact on the host communities.

In the words of Victoria Ayankemi Adeyinka, the call for unity is not merely aspirational but a theological and moral imperative. The Church, in all its expressions, must rise above the barriers of doctrinal rigidity and financial rivalry to embody the oneness for which Christ prayed and to which the global Church is called. Further highlights the impact of missionary activities in Nigeria, stating:

*"Missionary activities in Nigeria have resulted in numerous positive achievements, particularly in education and leadership. Missionary Churches communicate the Gospel through both word and deed, establishing Christian communities in ways that resonate with local cultures. This approach ensures that Christianity meets people's deepest needs, permeates their worldview, and enables them to follow Christ while remaining connected to their cultural identity."*¹⁵¹

A number of respondents in this study expressed the concern that many Pentecostal Church leaders remain inflexible regarding their denominational doctrines, which continues to hinder meaningful progress towards unity among the various Pentecostal denominations. This doctrinal rigidity has made it difficult for Churches to collaborate effectively, as each leader tends to emphasise their individual Church's theological distinctiveness over collective Christian identity. To address this issue, the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) can implemented certain measures aimed at fostering unity among its member Churches. One such initiative includes mandating that all Pentecostal leaders undergo foundational theological

¹⁵¹ V.A Adeyinka, Reflection on missionary activities in Nigeria. (Baylor University, 2022)

training from accredited Bible colleges. These institutions are expected to offer sound and biblically grounded instruction, providing a uniform standard of scriptural understanding among Church leaders. Respondents believed that exposure to a similar theological curriculum could contribute significantly to harmonising the teachings across different Churches. Such theological alignment, they argue, would not only create doctrinal consistency but also enhance mutual respect and collaboration among leaders of different Pentecostal assemblies.

This research highlights the need for the PFN to conduct periodic audits and evaluations of Bible colleges operated by Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. These audits should verify that their curricular content is thoroughly aligned with the teachings of the Bible. Furthermore, the PFN is encouraged to develop and disseminate a standardised curriculum that all Pentecostal-affiliated Bible colleges must adopt in the design and delivery of their theological programmes. Newly established Bible colleges should be subject to a rigorous accreditation process to ensure compliance with these standards before being permitted to operate.

In addition, the PFN should enforce a policy requiring that all Church planters and prospective Pentecostal leaders in the region possess at least a certificate from a recognised and accredited Bible college. This requirement would serve as a regulatory mechanism to curtail the proliferation of unverified and potentially heretical teachings, which often arise from poorly trained or self-ordained ministers. Periodic visits by PFN-appointed audit teams to local Churches should also be institutionalised to monitor doctrinal compliance and reinforce the integrity of Pentecostal teachings across the region.

5.2 Implications of the Research Findings

The findings of this study underscore the urgent need for greater unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. Theologically, unity is not merely a human aspiration but a

divine attribute, as clearly demonstrated in the nature of the Godhead, the Trinity. The early Church, as documented in the Acts of the Apostles, was characterised by deep unity in belief, practice, prayer, and communal living. This oneness served as a powerful testimony to both Jews and Gentiles, many of whom were drawn to the Christian faith as a result of the disciples' example. One of the respondents referenced Acts 2:46–47 (KJV):

“And they, continuing daily with one accord in the temple, and breaking bread from house to house, did eat their meat with gladness and singleness of heart, Praising God, and having favour with all the people. And the Lord added to the Church daily such as should be saved.”

This scripture was highlighted to emphasise the correlation between ecclesial unity and Church growth. As interpreted by one respondent, the early apostles did not rely heavily on structured evangelism; rather, their impact stemmed from their visible unity, mutual fellowship, and spiritual devotion. It was this internal harmony that, according to the respondent, moved God to continually add new believers to their numbers. However, the study also reveals that such expressions of communal unity—such as sharing meals, living in singleness of heart, and working together towards common spiritual goals—are significantly lacking in the contemporary Pentecostal movement in Southwest Nigeria. Respondents lamented the present-day absence of these foundational Christian practices, noting that the current Pentecostal landscape is often fragmented by competition, doctrinal disparities, and a general reluctance to submit to collective authority.

This deficiency in unity not only hinders internal cohesion among Pentecostal Churches but also weakens the public witness of the Church as a whole. The research suggests that renewed efforts toward theological standardisation, spiritual accountability, and intentional fellowship are essential steps toward reclaiming the unity that marked the early Church. It is only through such unified action that the Pentecostal Church in Southwest Nigeria can fulfil its divine mandate and serve as an authentic expression of the body of Christ.

The findings of this study further underscore the growing divide and persistent disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria, revealing that the gap continues to widen rather than diminish. This ongoing fragmentation presents an urgent call for strategic efforts to foster unity and collaboration within the Pentecostal movement. The study highlights the necessity for Church leaders to emulate the early apostles who, despite diversity in backgrounds and missions, were united in purpose and vision. Unity, as exemplified in the early Church, remains a cornerstone for spiritual resilience and institutional effectiveness in the contemporary Nigerian context. Respondents emphasized that the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN), as an umbrella body, holds a pivotal role in mitigating the current disunity. It was suggested that the PFN should intensify its efforts in organizing interdenominational programmes, conferences, and leadership seminars that prioritize unity, shared doctrine, and the collective mission of the Church. Through such initiatives, leaders can be educated on the theological and strategic significance of ecclesiastical unity. As some respondents asserted, *“Together as a Church, we stand strong against and overcome the devil; divided, we are weak, fall, and may be defeated.”* Another respondent affirmed, *“The devil and his agents, who are enemies of the Church, understand the power of unity in achieving victory—hence their strategic unity in fighting the Church.”* Likewise, the Church must be united to stand effectively against a united enemy.”

Moreover, the findings also addressed a critical underlying factor contributing to disunity—the emergence of diverse doctrinal orientations among new Pentecostal Churches. A recurring theme was the impact of ethnic, linguistic, and cultural biases in determining leadership appointments within Pentecostal denominations. It was observed that in many instances, deserving ministers are denied promotions due to their ethnic or linguistic differences from the founders or leadership hierarchy of certain Churches. In contrast, less qualified individuals who share ethnic or linguistic ties with the leadership are often elevated to such higher positions.

This discriminatory practice has the potential to breed dissatisfaction, resentment, and eventual secession, as discontented ministers and members may leave to establish their own independent Churches.

Such breakaway congregations often introduce modified doctrines, designed to attract adherents from their former Churches and appeal to broader audiences. This phenomenon not only exacerbates doctrinal fragmentation but also perpetuates division within the Pentecostal movement. Participants in the study identified this as a major threat to ecclesiastical unity, warning that these practices mirror the broader sociopolitical challenges in Nigeria—specifically, the entrenched divisions rooted in ethnicity, culture, and language. The Church, as a moral and spiritual institution, is thus called to transcend these societal divides and model inclusivity, fairness, and unity. If the Church continues to reflect the same ethnic and cultural prejudices prevalent in the larger society, it risks compromising its credibility and spiritual authority. Therefore, the findings advocate for a conscious and deliberate effort by Pentecostal Churches to promote unity, equity, and meritocracy in leadership and doctrinal integrity, thereby positioning the Church as a model of unity in diversity for the broader Nigerian society.

5.3 Contribution to Knowledge

The primary objective of this research is to critically examine and propose viable solutions to the persistent issue of disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. Rather than focusing on individual denominations or isolated congregations, this study adopts a holistic approach that addresses the broader implications of disunity within the collective Pentecostal movement and, by extension, the wider body of Christ. The study aims to provide significant contributions to ecclesiological discourse, with implications for theological practice, ministerial collaboration, and the structural coherence of Pentecostal Christianity in Nigeria.

Data collected through qualitative and quantitative survey instruments were systematically analyzed to validate the research hypothesis. The findings are expected to offer insights into several underlying causes of disunity and to inform practical strategies for fostering unity among diverse Pentecostal expressions. Key contributions emerging from the study include, but are not limited to, the following:

1. Doctrinal Differences as a Root Cause of Disunity

The research reveals that doctrinal divergence stands as a major factor contributing to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria. While many of these Churches profess adherence to biblical teachings, their interpretations and doctrinal emphases often diverge sharply. This fragmentation has led to theological disputes, schisms, and, in some cases, the birth of new religious movements within the Pentecostal spectrum.

Historically, the growth of Indigenous African Pentecostal Churches (IAPCs) can be traced to the friction arising from these doctrinal disagreements. Such fragmentation is not new; the Christian Church has contended with division since the first century. Pentecostalism, despite its vibrant spirituality and evangelistic zeal, is not immune to these forces of dissent. The study confirms that doctrinal variance continues to fuel institutional rivalry and undermine the unity of the Church as such:

A. Theological Disagreement on the Concept of Holiness

A particularly contentious theological issue among Pentecostal Churches pertains to the doctrine of holiness. Scripture, particularly in Pauline epistles, repeatedly emphasizes sanctified living. For example, Ephesians 4:24 admonishes believers to "put on the new man, which after God is created in righteousness and true holiness."

However, the interpretation of what constitutes true holiness varies significantly across Pentecostal denominations. Some respondents asserted that holiness is solely a spiritual

matter—an inward transformation of the 'new man'—and that once a person is saved, their salvation is eternally secure, irrespective of outward behavior. This view, often associated with the doctrine of "eternal security," is prevalent in certain Pentecostal circles.

Conversely, another group of respondents contested this perspective, maintaining that holiness encompasses both spiritual and physical dimensions. They argue that sanctified living must be evident not only in one's heart but also in external conduct. These opposing theological frameworks have created friction between Pentecostal groups, further exacerbated by inadequate theological dialogue and poor scriptural exegesis among some Church leaders and followers. The study identifies this misunderstanding as a significant contributor to inter-denominational fragmentation.

B. Controversies Surrounding Dress Code and Appearance

Though often overlooked in formal doctrinal discourse, issues relating to personal appearance and dress code have been shown to contribute to disunity within Pentecostalism. Several respondents noted that while this matter is rarely debated openly in doctrinal forums, it remains a persistent source of disagreement, particularly during religious conferences and inter-Church gatherings. Some traditional Pentecostal denominations, such as the African Indigenous Churches (AICs), have retained conservative standards concerning appearance. These Churches often display images depicting acceptable and unacceptable forms of dress, especially for female congregants. In such settings, individuals perceived to be dressed indecently—such as women with uncovered hair or revealing clothing—are often denied entry into worship services.

On the other hand, more contemporary Pentecostal Churches adopt a more liberal stance, encapsulated in the “come as you are” philosophy. One respondent recounted attending a service where female ministers wore clothing considered immodest by traditional standards,

and male attendees appeared in tight-fitting outfits and sportswear. The justification, according to members of that Church, lies in their doctrinal teaching that emphasizes the inward state of the heart as the sole measure of holiness before God. This tension between external modesty and internal sanctity reflects broader theological and cultural dynamics within Nigerian Pentecostalism. The researcher observed that such disagreements are deeply rooted in each Church's doctrinal orientation and reflect the larger ideological contest between conservatism and liberalism within the Pentecostal movement.

2. Financial Issues as a Catalyst for Schism in Pentecostal Churches

Financial disputes represent one of the most significant non-theological causes of division within Pentecostal Churches, particularly in Southwest Nigeria. According to research findings, the allocation and management of Church funds, although intended to support various spiritual and developmental projects, have often become sources of contention and fragmentation. Several respondents emphasized that the misuse, misappropriation, or outright embezzlement of Church finances has led to serious disagreements among Church leaders and congregants, ultimately culminating in the splintering of Church communities.

One respondent remarked: "Most of the new Churches we see today are offshoots of older, established Churches. Conflicts often emerge over how funds should be allocated for projects and programs. Allegations of financial misconduct and personal enrichment have caused disillusionment, leading to separations and the formation of new congregations. It's disheartening to witness Churches dividing over issues rooted in greed and corruption."

This underscores the crucial role of financial stewardship and accountability within the Church context. The research suggests that money, when not properly managed, possesses the capacity to corrupt and destabilize the fabric of communal worship and trust. As such, several respondents advocated for the appointment of financially responsible individuals—those of

proven integrity and tested moral character—to oversee Church resources. They stressed that financial mismanagement has not only contributed to internal strife but also limited the Church’s capacity to fund religious and social initiatives that could benefit broader society.

Furthermore, many expressed concern that financial fraud has become systemic in some Pentecostal circles, with efforts to implement reforms often ignored or resisted. This has fostered a recurring pattern where factions break away to form new Churches under the guise of reform, only for similar issues to re-emerge. Thus, financial mismanagement continues to be a recurrent and deeply entrenched cause of Church division.

3. Personal Factors and Individualism in Church Disunity

Beyond financial concerns, personal attitudes and individualistic tendencies among Church members and leaders have also emerged as significant contributors to division within Pentecostal Churches. The Pentecostal tradition places strong emphasis on personal experience and spiritual expression, which can result in diverse interpretations of Christian teachings. Respondents noted that individual perspectives—shaped by personality, background, and spiritual disposition—often influence how faith is practiced and understood within congregations. One respondent observed: *"People bring their own preferences and personalities into how they perceive and practice Christianity. These subjective interpretations can lead to tensions, particularly when there is a lack of alignment with the broader vision or doctrine of the Church."*

Such tensions can become exacerbated in environments where individualism supersedes collective identity. Some Church members prioritize personal success and recognition over communal progress and spiritual unity. This attitude, often expressed through a sense of spiritual superiority or exclusivism, leads to divisions not only within a single denomination but also across the broader Christian spectrum. The situation becomes further complicated

when individual followers engage in campaigns against non-denominational Churches or other religious traditions, thereby widening the rift. Another respondent highlighted that within Pentecostal Churches, varying degrees of spiritual expression—ranging from fanaticism to conservatism—can coexist uneasily. Over time, differences in zeal and interpretation can give rise to internal factions, especially when fueled by personal motivations and ego. This dynamic was described as particularly dangerous when leaders prioritize personal ambition over the collective interest of the congregation.

Moreover, the prevalence of megalomania among some Church leaders was cited as a dominant force behind internal Church crises. Several respondents noted that such leaders often impose their personal will on Church affairs, leaving little room for collaboration or dissent. This ego-driven leadership style breeds resentment, fosters factionalism, and ultimately contributes to Church fragmentation. In sum, both personal ambitions and the unchecked egos of leaders and followers alike have been shown to undermine Church unity, fostering an environment where division becomes almost inevitable.

4. Cultural and Traditional Influences as a Source of Division within Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria

A significant yet often overlooked factor contributing to division and disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria is the pervasive influence of cultural affiliation and traditional solidarity among Church leaders. This phenomenon, rooted in the broader sociocultural fabric of the region, has infiltrated ecclesiastical structures and leadership dynamics. One respondent in this study highlighted how conservatism, as both a religious and cultural tradition, has shaped not only internal Church practices but also the wider societal norms. According to a school of thought, “Due to the proliferation of local Pentecostal Churches within society, many social groups have unconsciously adopted norms and traditions

that originate from doctrinal interpretations.”¹⁵² This observation suggests that religious conservatism within the Pentecostal movement is not insulated but rather deeply intertwined with prevailing local customs and communal identities.

Another participant noted that leadership appointments and the promotion of ministers within some Pentecostal Churches are influenced more by shared cultural and ethnic affiliations with the Church founder than by spiritual merit or ministerial competence. Such ethnocentric bias fosters internal conflicts and creates an environment where meritocracy is undermined. Consequently, dissatisfaction among members often ensues, leading to schisms, fragmentation, and ultimately, disunity within the Church. This dynamic reflects the intrusion of broader societal prejudices—such as ethnic favoritism and tribal allegiance—into ecclesiastical governance, thereby compromising the spiritual integrity and unity of the Church.

The broader implication of such divisions is the deterioration of the public image of Pentecostalism in the region. When Churches become embroiled in cultural politics, they risk being perceived as ethnoreligious institutions rather than as inclusive spiritual communities. This undermines their evangelical mission and weakens the moral authority of Pentecostalism within Nigerian society. The study affirms that ecclesiastical unity remains a critical necessity for the growth and sustainability of Pentecostal Churches in Southwestern Nigeria. However, respondents expressed divergent views on the practical pathways to achieving this unity. Some proposed the organisation of regular inter-Church programmes, such as seminars, workshops, and conferences, that would bring together Pentecostal leaders across denominations for sustained dialogue and collaboration. These initiatives, they argued, would serve to build mutual trust and encourage shared visions.

¹⁵² M. T. Ndemanu, “*Traditional African religions and their influences on the worldviews of Bangwa people of Cameroon*”: January 2018, pp 70 - 84

Others suggested the need for joint evangelistic efforts, such as crusades, outreach missions, and community engagement programmes. These collective activities, they maintained, would reinforce the importance of unity in the Body of Christ and create a functional space for collaboration. Emphasis was also placed on revisiting and upholding the core objectives of the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN), which are summarised as follows:

Aims and Purposes of the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN)

1. To foster unity among all Pentecostal Churches, ministries, and believers for the purpose of fellowship, encouragement, and mutual inspiration.
2. To create a platform of solidarity against common adversities, especially during times of persecution or opposition to Pentecostal tenets.
3. To implement joint initiatives for the advancement of the full gospel, including activities in Christian education, literature distribution, evangelism, and the establishment of Bible colleges.
4. To represent the interests of Pentecostal believers to governmental and interdenominational bodies while defending the doctrinal integrity of the faith.
5. To formulate and enforce doctrinal standards and ethical codes that identify and preserve the authenticity of Pentecostal practice and belief.

Objectives and Goals of the PFN

1. To help Pentecostal believers maintain the unity of the Spirit in the bond of peace, both among themselves and with other Christian denominations within their communities.
2. To uphold doctrinal purity by promoting sound theological teachings rooted in Biblical truth, while avoiding doctrinal extremism and practices that might discredit the Church's public witness (cf. 2 Peter 2:2).

3. To crystallise the essence of Pentecostal spirituality by ensuring that its doctrines and values are not only correctly articulated but also embodied in the daily lives and worship of believers, in alignment with the admonitions of Scripture (cf. 2 Timothy 3:5).

Despite the PFN's articulated mission, some respondents expressed concern that the Fellowship has fallen short of its core mandate. According to this group, the PFN has not adequately enforced its standards nor held Churches accountable to the ethical and spiritual principles it claims to uphold. Instead, there have been allegations of indiscipline, internal corruption, and administrative laxity. One respondent lamented: *"Had the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria remained committed to its founding vision, particularly in the enforcement of its aims and objectives, unity among Pentecostal Churches in the Southwest would have been significantly improved."*

Another cohort of respondents believed that, in the absence of decisive action by the PFN, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) should intervene. They argued that CAN, by virtue of its overarching Christian ecumenical vision—as reflected in its motto, “That they all may be one” (John 17:21)—is well-positioned to mediate and facilitate unity among Pentecostal denominations when the PFN proves ineffective. This reflects a broader expectation that ecclesiastical umbrella bodies must play a more active role in promoting unity, particularly in contexts where cultural, ethnic, and doctrinal differences threaten to undermine the integrity of the Christian witness.

Objectives of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN)

The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) has articulated several foundational objectives that guide its operations and engagement with Churches and society at large. These include:

A. To serve as a unifying platform for the Christian Church in Nigeria, in alignment with the intercessory prayer of Jesus Christ as recorded in John 17:21: *"That they all may be one."* This reflects a theological imperative for ecclesiastical unity across denominations.

B. To foster mutual understanding, social harmony, and peaceful coexistence among diverse groups and strata within Nigerian society through the dissemination of the Gospel message.

C. To function as a consultative and coordinating body through which member Churches can engage in dialogue, issue joint communiqués, and initiate collective actions on matters of mutual concern.

D. To act as a vigilant guardian for the spiritual and moral integrity of the Nigerian nation, offering critical interventions on socio-religious issues where necessary.

According to a specific group of respondents, CAN holds a particularly crucial role in promoting unity within the broader Christian community and, more specifically, among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria, with emphasis on Lagos. These respondents argue that CAN is instrumental in developing regulatory frameworks that enhance inter-Church relations, foster collaboration among Christian leaders, and promote cohesion within the wider body of Christ.

5.4 Recommendations and Suggestions for Further Research

5.4.1 Recommendations

There is a growing and persistent call for unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria, particularly in Lagos. The benefits of such unity far outweigh the drawbacks of continued fragmentation. Notably, Jesus Christ's prayer for unity among his followers before His ascension underscores its spiritual and ecclesial significance. Disunity breeds conflict, discord, and division, whereas unity promotes harmony, mutual understanding, and doctrinal

coherence. Unity, therefore, is not merely a strategic necessity but a divine injunction—one that reflects the very essence of the Christian faith. From a biblical perspective, unity represents the divine orchestration of diverse individuals—spanning ethnic, cultural, and socioeconomic differences—into a single spiritual family through faith (cf. 1 Corinthians 12:27; Galatians 3:26–28). Achieving unity, though challenging, is not unattainable. In the context of Pentecostalism, concerted efforts by both the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) and the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) are vital. These two institutions must work in synergy to promote peace, unity, and doctrinal consistency among member Churches.

Doctrinal Standardization: The PFN should endorse and support accredited theological institutions to provide unified doctrinal training to Pentecostal leaders. This approach would mitigate doctrinal proliferation and theological dissonance, which currently contribute to fragmentation within the Pentecostal community in Southwest Nigeria. Furthermore, CAN should play a supervisory role akin to that of the National Universities Commission (NUC), by developing a standard theological curriculum to ensure sound doctrinal teaching. Achieving this may require legislative backing from the National Assembly to regulate theological institutions across Nigeria.

Financial Governance: One of the major sources of division in Pentecostal Churches is financial mismanagement. According to both scholarly opinions and respondents' insights, the lack of financial transparency has caused significant rifts. To prevent such issues, Church leadership should prioritize the appointment of individuals of impeccable character, integrity, and moral rectitude to oversee Church funds and financial operations.

Cultural and Ethnic Integration: As posited by sociologist Emile Durkheim, religion and society are deeply intertwined. Nigerian society is stratified along ethnic, religious, and political lines—factors that have historically impeded national unity. While such divisions may

persist in broader society, they must not permeate the Church. Ethnicity and regionalism should not be criteria for Church leadership appointments. Drawing from biblical examples (Acts 6:3, Acts 1:24), Church leaders should select individuals for leadership based on spiritual maturity, honesty, and divine guidance rather than ethnic affiliation. This principle promotes trust, equity, and inclusivity within Church governance.

5.4.2 Suggestions for Further Research

In light of the findings, limitations, and theoretical implications of this study, the following avenues for future research are recommended:

- a.** A comprehensive evaluation of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) with particular focus on its operational effectiveness in fulfilling its stated mission and vision, especially in terms of fostering unity among Nigerian Churches.
- b.** An in-depth case study on *The Role of Financial Stewardship in Missionary Expansion*, with a specific focus on the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), examining how financial strategies contribute to missionary success or challenges.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Achunike. H. C. *Dreams of Heaven: A Modern Response of Christianity in North Western Igbo land*, Onitsha, Nigeria: African-FEP, 1995
- Adedibu, Babatunde. Chapter 3 "Introduction to Pentecostalism and Ecumenism" 2019
- Adeyinka V. A. *Reflection on missionary activities in Nigeria*. Baylor University, 2022
- Adler, J. "*Varieties of Spiritual Experience: Shen in Neo-Confucian Discourse*" 2004
- Allan Anderson, & Walter Hollenweger, *Pentecostal After a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition*, Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999.
- Allan Anderson. *An Introduction to Pentecostalism* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.
- Allan Anderson. *African Reformation: African Initiated Christianity in the 20th Century* (Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press, 2001.
- Allan Anderson. *An introduction to Pentecostalism, 2nd edn*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- Alokan, Peter et al, American Journal of Social Management Sciences "*Critical Analyses of Church Politics and Crises within the Indigenous Christianity in Nigeria*" March 2011.
- Alvarado, J.E, "*Exploring Africanisms in Latin American Pentecostalism*," in V. Synan & M. Álvarez (eds.), *Global renewal Christianity: Spirit-empowered movements past, present, and future, vol. 2: Latin America*, Charisma House, Lake Mary, 2016.
- Andre , B, "*Ecumenism in Jean Yves Lacoste*", (ed.), Encyclopedia of Christian Theology, Vol. 1. New York: Routeledge 2005.
- Andrew Othuke Akpeli: "*Explaining the Spread of Pentecostalism in Nigeria*", 22 May 2012.
- Anih S. *Religious Ecumenism and Education for Toerance in Nigeria*, Enugu: Snaap Press Ltd., 1992.
- Anih, S. *Towards A Nigerian Ecumenical Education*, Enugu: Snaap Press Ltd., 1987.
- Archbishop Vitaly of Montreal and Canada, "*Ecumenism*", a Report to the Sobor Bishops
- Asamoah-Gyadu, J. K. "*Pentecostalism and the influence of primal realities in Africa*", in H.D. Hunter & N. Ormerod (eds.), *The many faces of global Pentecostalism*, Charisma House, Lake Mary 2013.
- Asamoah-Gyadu, J. Kwabena, Chapter Fifteen: "*Born of Water and Spirit*": *Pentecostal / Charismatic Christianity in Africa*, The University of Pretoria. Library Services, 2013.

- Austin Flannery. *Vatican II Council: Decree on Ecumenism*, Unitatis Redintegratio. Dublin: Dominican, 1988.
- Awojobi , Peter O. “ *Leadership Conflict in the Nigerian Church*” 2011 Global Christianity Pew Forum on Religion and Public Life,: “*A report on the size and distribution of the World Christian Population*”, 2011.
- Ayegboyin . Deji. *Rediscovering and Fostering Unity in the Body of Christ: The Nigerian Experience*, 2009
- Azino Efe, *Proliferation of Churches and corruption in Nigeria: Understanding the irony*, Academic, Education Assessed 6th May 2015.
- Bediako Kwame. *Christianity in Africa: The renewal of a non-Western religion*. Orbis Book 1996
- Bediako, K. *Christianity in Africa: The Renewal of a Non-Western Religion*, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh. 1995.
- Berdyaev, N. A. “*Orthodoxy and Ecumenism*”, in <http://www.chebucto.ns.ca/philosophy/sin>
- Boyd Bible Dictionary, 219, 1980.
- Catherine L. Albanese - *America: Religions and Religion*, California, wadsworth, 1981
- Cecil M. Robeck, Jr. *The Azusa Street Mission and Revival: The Birth of the Global Pentecostal Movement*, Nashville, tn: Nelson Reference and Electronic, 2006.
- Cheryl Bridges Johns. *Pentecostal Formation*, Wipf & Stock Publishers, Oregon, United States, 2010.
- Chijama Ogibu, “*Survey is contained in an Article Religious population*” Chijama City Newspaper 13 August, 2012.
- Chitando, E. & Biri, Magaya’s K. Walter, “*Prophetic Healing and Deliverance*” (PH.D.) *Ministries and Pentecostalism in Zimbabwe: a preliminary study with particular reference to ecumenism. Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 2016.
- Chitando, E. & Biri, K. Walter Magaya’s *Prophetic Healing and Deliverance* (PH.D.) *Ministries and Pentecostalism in Zimbabwe: a preliminary study with particular reference to Ecumenism. Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 2016.
- Corpus. I.A.B, Christian Today online magazine *Church and Reflections on the Nigerian situation*”, 2018
- Cox H. *The Author(s)*. Published by Taylor & Francis. Florida USA 2004
- Cox, H. *Fire from heaven: The rise of Pentecostal spirituality and the reshaping of Christianity in the twenty-first century*, Addison-Wesley, Reading 1995.

- Cox, H. "Some personal Reflections on Pentecostalism," Pneuma Publishing Ltd, Lagos Nigeria, 1993.
- David J. Engelsma, "Pentecostalism: Its Identity, History, and Influence", 2001
- David J. Engelsma: Pentecostalism: Its Identity, History, and Influence (prca.org)1995
- David Westerlund, *Global Pentecostalism: Encounter with Other Religious Tradition*, (I.B Tauris & Co Ltd., 2009.
- David. B. Barrett, "Annual Statistical Table on Global Mission", (Regent University, Virginia Beach, Virginia, 2003.
- Diara, B.C.D. *Anglican Spirituality: The Practice of Balanced Christianity*, Enugu: Computer
- Duke. Akamisoko. *S Ajayi in the Lokoja Area*, Ibadan: Sefer Books Ltd, 84. 2002.
- Early T, "Ecumenism" in *Encyclopedia Dictionary of Religion* (Eds) Washington DC: Ekpunobi, E "We Are Closer Than We Think: An Analysis of Contemporary Issues In ecumenism" 2020.
- Elaigwu, J. I. *Essay in Governance and Society, Nigeria*: Adonis & Abbey Publishers, 2021.
- Emilie Durkheim. *The Elementary Forms of the Religious life*, Publisher Dover Publications New Your USA 1912.
- Eregare, E.O. *An African Christian Church History: Seventh-day Adventist Cosmology in the Edo-Delta States: & Ecumenical Initiatives*, Lagos, Nigeria: Christ Coming Books 2013.
- Eregare, E.O, Ekpendu I.C., & Adesina S. "Ecumenism and the Church in the Postmodern Era: Historical, Biblio-Theological and Missiological Appraisal", *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry*, 2017.
- Eregare, E.O. 'Ecumenism and the Church in the Post-modern Era: Historical, Biblio-Theological and Missiological Appraisal *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry* Vol. 15, 2017.
- Freeman D. *Pentecostalism and Development Churches, NGOs and Social Change in Africa*. Publisher: Palgrave Macmillian 2012
- Frestadius. Simo "European Pentecostalism: A European Past and a Pentecostal Future," *Pneuma* 2020
- G.E. Igwe. *Church Union in Nigeria*, Enugu: Ark Publication, 2000
- Gastón Espinosa, *The origin of Global Pentecostalism*, Publisher Duke University Press, USA 2014.
- Glyn Leonard. *The Lower Niger and Its Tribe*, London: Frank Class, 1968.

- Green W. A. *Sociology An Analysis of Life in Modern Society* New York, published by McGraw-Hill Book Co., 1952.
- Hollenweger, J. (eds), *Pentecostal After a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition* (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999), Water J. Hollenweger, *Pentecostalism: Origins and Developments Worldwide*, Hendrickson Publishers, Peabody, Massachusetts USA, 1997.
- Idowu E. B *African Traditional Religion: A Definition*, London: SCM press Ltd, 1978.
- Ihejirika, W. C. *An Audience Ethnography on the Role of the Mass Media in the Process of Conversion of Catholics to the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria*. Roma: Pontificia Universita Gregoriana. 2004.
- Isichei, E. *A History of Christianity in Africa: From antiquity to the present*. Grand Rapids, Mich: Eerdmans. 1995
- Isichei, F. I. *Catholic Approach to the Charismatic Renewal*, Asaba: His Joy Books, 1988.
- J. G. Melton: *Pentecostalism* Editor of Encyclopedia Britannica, 10th March 2022.
- John, O, “*Christianity and other Religions: Contemporary Theological Currents in the Excerpt from an interview he granted Mathew Irekiigbe*, The Sun Newspaper, 2002
- Jonathan Mbiriyaamveka: *The Herald journal* April 2014
- Jorome, P. *World evangelism oxford*: oxford University Press. 2002
- Kaigama, Ignatius . A. *Dialogue of Life, an Urgent Necessity for Nigerian Muslims and Christians*, Jos: Fab Educational Books, 2006.
- Kalu, O. *A Discursive Interpretation of African Pentecostalism*, Mission Studies 2007, 20:1-39, Matthew Ojo, *The End-Time Army: Charismatic Movement in Modern Nigeria*, Trenton NJ: African world Press 2006
- Kalu, O. *African Pentecostalism: An Introduction*. New York: Oxford University Press. 2008.
- Karl Marx. *A passing remark in a book of philosophy a contribution to the Critique of Hegel's Philosophy of Right*. 1843
- Kasper W. *A Handbook of Spiritual Ecumenism*, New York: New City Press, 2007. 20
- Kato, B.H *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Kenya: Evangel Publishing House. 1975
- Kitause H. R. and Achunike, H. C. The Future of Prosperity Gospel in Nigeria, *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, Volume 3. Issue 7, 2015.
- Kobia, T, The General Secretary of The World Council of Churches, A keynote Address, Koffeman, L. J. The Vulnerability of the Church – Ecclesiological Observations, *Scriptura*, 102(1), 2009.

- Kunuba, A. C. *That they may be one (UT UNUM SINT) John 17:21*. A paper presented at the CATHAN conference, Lugbe, Abuja. 22nd -25th April, 2014.
- Leslie N. *The household of God*, publisher: SCM press Greater London UK. 1953.
- Marongwe, N. and Maposa, N. Richard PHDS, *Gosprenurship, Globalization and the Pentecostal 'New Wave' in Zimbabwe*: In Afro-Asian Journal of Social Sciences. Volume VI, No. 1. *Quarter 1*, 2015
- Martins, R. D. *Church Conflicts: How Do You Settle Church Conflicts?* A Radio Bible Class Publication, USA. 1986.
- Mathew A. Ojo. "Consonance and Dissonance in the Doctrinal Emphasis of Prosperity among Nigerian Pentecostal" in African Journal of Pentecostal and Charismatic Studies (AJPCS), Vol.1, No.1, February, 2013
- Mathew A. Ojo. "The End Time Army: Charismatic Movements in Modern Nigeria" Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press; and "Eschatology and African Society: The Critical Point of Disjunction", *Ogbomoso Journal of Theology*, (Africa World Press 2006).
- Mathew A. Ojo. *The End- Time Army; Charismatic movement in modern Nigeria*, Africa World Press Nigeria 2006.
- Maxwell. D, *The Rise and Fall of the Dutch Reformed Church (DRC): In the Victoria Circle 1888-150: 2005*. A *Dissenting View of the Church's Alleged Invention of Chikaranga* with Particular Reference to the Chibi Circuit, Unpublished paper presented at the New Dimensions in History Seminar Paper No. 5. Department of History, University of Zimbabwe 28 May 2004. McBride, Dennis (1993). A Survey of the History and Distinctives of Pentecostalism.
- McCain, D. *The Metamorphosis of Nigerian Pentecostalism. From Signs and Wonders in the Church to Service and Influence in Society*. (2013). In Miller. D. E., Sargeant, K.H., and Flory, R. (Eds.) (2013). *Spirit and Power. The Growth and Global Impact of Pentecostalism*, New York: Oxford University Press 2013.
- Meyer, B. "Pentecostalism and Neo-Liberal Capitalism: Faith, Prosperity and Vision in African Pentecostal- Charismatic Churches," *Journal for the Study of Religion*, 2007.
- Michaelson. W. Grangerg, "The future of Ecumenism In The 21st Century" 2005
- MLA style: "The Gospel and African Religion." The Free Library, 2000, World Council of Churches 22 Mar. 2022.
- Musa. A. B. Gaiya "The Pentecostal revolution in Nigeria" 2002.
- Musoni Phillip, *African Pentecostalism and Sustainable Development: A Study on the Zimbabwe Assemblies of God Africa, Forward In Faith Church*: In *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*. Volume 2, Issue October 2013.

- Musoni, P. "The Rise and Fall of the Dutch *Development: A Study on the Zimbabwe Assemblies of God Africa, Forward In Faith Church: In International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention. Volume 2*", 10, October 2013.
- Ndiokwere, N. I 'The African Church Today and Tomorrow, Prospects and Challenges', Vol. 1. Nigeria: Effective Key 1994.
- Nnebedum, O. E. *Ecumenism in Nigeria: The Roman Catholic contribution. An Unpublished M.A. Project submitted to the Department of Religion, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. 2009*
- Norman. A. Stahi and James R. King, "Understanding and using trustworthiness in qualitative research *Journal of development education*" vol 44 2020.
- Obiora, F. K. *The Divine Deceit: Business in Religion*. Enugu: Optimal. 1998
- Ogibu, C "Survey is contained in an article *Religious population*" Chijama City Newspaper
- Okonkwo, M. "Back to the Bible", *Sermon at Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria 8th Biennial Conference, Lagos. 2005*
- Olalekan Adetayo, "Global Index of Religiosity and Atheism," Gallop International 2012.
- Olatunji, D. "Oral Interview on Pentecostalism in Nigeria," 2016.
- Omenyo, C. 'African Pentecostalism', in C.M. Robeck & A. Young, The Cambridge Oyewo, K. *Pentecostalism and Conflict Resolution Strategies*. A thesis at the Immanuel College of Theology, University of Ibadan, 2002.
- Omenyo, C. 'African Pentecostalism', in C.M. Robeck & A. Young, The Cambridge companion to Pentecostalism, Cambridge University Press, New York. 2014.
- Osunwokeh, Fr. Clement I. *Ecumenism and Biblical Interpretation: Nigerian Experience in the Operation of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN)*, Volume 2, Issue—3, August 2014.
- Otite, O. and Isaac, O.A. *Community Conflicts in Nigeria: Management, Resolution and Transformation*, Spectrum Books Limited, Ibadan. 1999.
- Oyalana A.S. "Attempts at Church Ecumenism in, Nigeria" journal on religious study 1996
- P.A. Heers, "The Missionary Origins of Modern Ecumenism: Milestone Leading Up To
- Paton, D.M. (ed) *Breaking Barriers*, Nairobi, cited in C.P. Ibebuike, 1975, London 1976
- Peel J.D. *Religious and the Making of the Yoruba* Indiana University Press, USA, 2003
- Peel, J. D *Religious and the Making of the Yoruba*, Indiana University Press, USA, 2003.
- Peel, J.D and Matthews. A. Ojo *The End-Time Army: Charismatic Movement in Modern Nigeria*, (Africa World Press, Inc, Trenton, NJ USA, 2006), and Ruth Marshall, 2009,

- Political Spirituality: The Pentecostal Revolution*, The University of Chicago press Ltd., 2003.
- Pew Research Center “*Religion ad Public Life, The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections*”, 2010 Rausch, T. *Global Catholicism: Profiles and Polarities*, New York: Orbis Books. 2021.
- R.V. Sinner, “*Ecumenism In The 21st Century: Thesis for Discussion*” A Work Presented To Rausch, T. *Global Catholicism: Profiles and Polarities*, New York: Orbis Books 2021.
- Reuben Abati: “*Rape & the Senior Pastor of COZA*”. Newsdairy July 2, 2019.
- Salihu, J. *Koinonia: The basis of the Church’s ecumenical involvement*, A paper presented at the CATHAN conference, Lugbe, Abuja. 22nd -25th April, 2014.
- Segreda, L. “*Evangelization and the Holy Spirit in an Urban and Multicultural*”, 1993.
- Suenens, L.J. *A New Pentecost?* New The Seabury Press York: INC., 1975.
- Synan, Vinson. *The Magazine: The world growth at 19 million a year*, Nov 1999
- Synan, Vinson. *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 2005
- Tavard, G.H. *The Church Tomorrow*. London Larton, Longman and Todd Ltd., 1965.
- Thomas, V.V. *Dalit Pentecostalism – Spirituality of the Empowered Poor*, Bangalore: Asian
- Todd M. Johnson and Peter F. Crossing, Status of Global Mission, in the context of AD 1800–2025. *International Bulletin of Missionary Research*, 2015.
- Turner, Harold W. *Religious innovation in Africa: Collected Essay on New Religious Movement*, G.K Hall Press, Boston USA, 1979.
- Ukah, A. Advertising God: *Nigerian Christian Video-Films and the Power of Consumer Culture Journal of Religion in Africa* Vol. 33, Fasc. 2, 203-231. 2010. Pew Research Center (2015). Religion ad Public Life, The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections, 2010-2050 <https://www.pewforum.org/2015/04/02/religious-projections-2010-2050/>
- Ukah, A. *African Christianity: Features, Promises and Problems*, Department of Anthropology and African Studies, 2007. <https://researchgate.net/publication/45667178> Retrieved 12-10-2018
- Ukpong, D. P. *The presence and impact of Pentecostalism in Nigeria*, Posted online at: www.glopent.net/.../presence-and-impact-of-pentecostalism-in-nigeria 2006
- USCCB (United State Conference of Catholic Bishops), “*Ecumenical and International*
- Vaccaro de Petrella, L. S ‘*The Tension between Evangelism and Social Action in the Pentecostal Movement in the International Review of Mission*’, 1986.
- Vason , W. “*Ecumenism” The Orthodox Faith*”, <http://www.orthodoxfaith.com>

- Vason, W. *The origin of Pentecostalism*, Cambridge: Haward University Press, 2010.
- Vinson Synan. The Holiness-Pentecostal Movement in the United States Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1971, .inson Synan, *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 2005
- Vinson, Synan. *The Origins of the Pentecostal Movement*, Regent University 20
- Waliggo, J. M. "New Attitude Towards Other Churches" in A. Shorter and Co. (eds.) *Towards African Christian Maturity*. Kampala: St. Paul's Publications. 1987
- Walter J. Hollenweger identified Pentecostalism as having five roots: catholic, evangelical, critical, ecumenical, and black oral. "The Black Roots of Pentecostalism," in *Pentecostals after a Century: Global Perspectives on a Movement in Transition*, eds. Allan H. Anderson and Walter J. Hollenweger, Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999.
- Walter J. Hollenweger. *The Pentecostals*, SCM Press Ltd, London UK 1972
- Water, J. Hollenweger "After Twenty Years Research on Pentecostalism", *International Review of Mission* 1986
- Weber, M. *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, E-library Edition London: Routledge Classic, 2005.7
- William, James. *The Varieties of Religious Experience: A study in human nature*, LC Class BR110 JB 1902
- Williamson, S.G. *Akan Religion and the Christian Faith: A comparative study of the impact of two religions*, Ghana University Press, Accra. 1965

APPENDIX

THE REDEEMED CHRISTIAN BIBLE COLLEGE, MAIN CAMPUS

SCHOOL OF HIGHER DEGREE

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Research question 1

To what extent is unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria regarded as important in accordance with biblical teachings?

1. There is nothing like unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

2. In unity, the Churches can stand

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

3. No meaningful thing can be achieved without unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

4. When there is unity there is progress

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

5. Even God, may not break the cord of unity easily

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

6. All enemy efforts are useless when there is unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

7. Churches need to work towards unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

8. Churches need to work towards unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

9. Churches need to pray for unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

10. Churches need programmes encouraging unity

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

Research question 2

To what extent is unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria regarded as important in accordance with biblical teachings?

11. The Bible teaches the same doctrine

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

12. Churches only have problems interpreting the doctrine of the Bible

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

13. Doctrine has divided us in the way we handle them

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

14. Church leaders are not sincere most times, interpreting

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

15. Leaders interpret doctrine just to favour them

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

16. I am of Apollo, I am of Paul is the order of the day now

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

17. God uses word standards to checkmate excuses of leaders' self-doctrinal practice

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

18. Church leaders' involvement in doctrine needs to be dealt with

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

19. Pentecostal Churches are more divided among themselves than main-line Churches

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

20. God did not give us doctrine to divide us

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

Research Question 3

To what extent does the pursuit of financial supremacy contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

21. We cannot all belong to the same denomination

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

22. Even Jesus recognised another religious group with the same purpose

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

23. Not all leaders of Churches are called

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

24. Many are in the ministry for food's sake

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

25. Most Churches programmers are geared towards money making

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

26. Serious priority is giving to money making than spirituality

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

27. Many Pastor are interested in member pocket rather than their soul

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

28. Many evangelised just for the numerical size

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

29. Some Pastors do not boarder whether members make it to heaven

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

30. Most leaders need a change of orientation toward money in the Church

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

Research Question 4 –

To what extent do competition in congregational size, membership growth, and the expansion of worship centres contribute to disunity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

31. Many boast their congregational size

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

32. Many leaders are proud of their worship centre

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

33. Many are concerned with membership numbers and not those that will make it to heaven

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

34. Some leaders waste a fortune on worship centres rather than on member's welfare

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

35. Some evangelise only the rich

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

36. Some value their properties more than member's souls

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

37. Some leaders consider other leaders' Church size before they are invited

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

38. Some ladders look down on other men of God they consider less privilege

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

39. There are so many unhealthy rivalries among men of God

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

40. Many are too proud of their self-achievement

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

Research Question 5

To what extent are Church leaders unwilling to relinquish doctrinal practices in order to promote unity among Pentecostal Churches in Southwest Nigeria?

41. Leaders teach doctrine to divide rather than to the unit

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

42. Christian Association of Nigeria need to do something in this respect

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

43. Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria should do something too

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

44. Pride make it difficult for most Pastors to work with others

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

45. Some Pastor suffer an inferiority complex in allowing their members to fellowship in other Church

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

46. A superiority complex will not make some Pastors to have anything to do with other men of God

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

47. A forum to iron out differences among Pentecostal Churches in need

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

48. Pastors need to review how they teach doctrine

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

49. Doctrines dissemination should not divide us

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		

50. We need to adhere to Christ's prayer for the unity of the Church in John Chapter 17

Variable	No of Respondent	Percentage %
Strongly Agreed		
Agreed		
Disagreed		
Strongly Disagreed		
Total		